

Picking pearls from the Silk Road: Insights into the spider (Arachnida, Araneae) diversity in Georgia from the Caucasus Barcode of life project. Part II

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Abstract

Spiders collected during field trips and by spontaneous hand collection throughout Georgia between the years 2006 and 2023 were determined to species and partially assisted by genetic barcoding of the COI gene. Among the resulting 297 species, 100 species, 25 genera, and 1 family were recorded from Georgia for the first time, of which 18 species and 5 genera were recorded for the first time from the entire Caucasus. Of the 283 barcoded specimens representing 150 species, 26 were barcoded for the first time. 140 diagnostic drawings of 76 preserved specimens, along with photos of 15 preserved (Supplementary File) and one alive species, are provided. *Baryphyma proclive* (Simon, 1884), *Pritha pallida* (Kulczyński, 1897), and *Zelotes khostensis* Kovblyuk & Ponomarev, 2008 are indicated as the species with an Italo-Caucasian disjunctive distribution.

Key words

Aranei, biodiversity, faunistics, new records, South Caucasus

Introduction

It is widely accepted that the Great Silk Road route connected China with Central, East, South, Southeast, and West Asia, East Africa, and Southern Europe. Additionally, there is evidence that at least Western Georgia was highly involved in trading, the so-called northern branch of the Great Silk Road (Lordkipanidze 2002; Jamburia 2022). These obviously close trade relations have prompted us to examine the arachnofauna of this region more closely. The present survey represents the second and largest contribution in the series of articles devoted to the faunistic study of Georgian spiders. To date, over 650 spider species from 261 genera comprised of 43 families are known from Georgia,

which is $\approx 50\%$ of the total diversity of the Caucasus region (Otto 2023). Although there are several recent publications dealing with the description of new species and systematic revisions or records of taxa new to the araneofauna of Georgia (Jäger and Otto 2007; Otto and Tanasevitch 2015; Ponomarev and Komarov 2015; Marusik and Koponen 2017; Mikhailov et al. 2017; Zonstein et al. 2018; Marusik et al. 2019, 2020; Ponomarev et al. 2019), large-scale faunistic surveys have been scarce (Otto and Japoshvili 2018; Seropian et al. 2023), while given the overall biodiversity of the Caucasian spiders (>1100 species) and their distributional patterns (Otto 2023), the estimated number should be not less than 900 local species. As a result of the previous part of this series, two genera and seven species were record-

ed from Georgia for the first time, of which two species appeared to be new to the Caucasus region (Seropian et al. 2023). In the present study, we provide records of an additional 100 species new to the fauna of Georgia, of which 20 taxa have never been previously recorded in the Caucasus. The collecting information for each record is provided in detail, together with a discussion and remarks concerning the more interesting species and records, supported by photos of specimens and drawings of their morphological details.

Material and methods

Sampling methods

The main part of the studied material was collected within the framework of the Caucasus Barcode of Life (CaBOL) project, being the most ambitious arthropod inventories ever performed in Georgia by the members of the GGBC (Georgian-German Biodiversity Center) and the CaBOL team of the Institute of Ecology, Ilia State University (<https://ggbc.eu/>). Most of the samples were collected during expeditions and short trips to different parts of Georgia (including both protected and unprotected) via aspirators, soil sifters, hand collecting, and beating methods. Sampling details are given below.

Collected specimens were preserved in 96% ethanol and stored in a freezer under -22°C at the scientific collections of Ilia State University (Georgia, Tbilisi), Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig (ZFMK) (Germany, Bonn), and the personal collection of Stefan Otto (Germany, Leipzig). Unique ID numbers of the preserved material (CaBOL-ID, ZFMK-TIS, and KVS/KBS) indicate the depositories (Ilia State University, Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig, and the personal collection of Stefan Otto, respectively). Identification was done by the authors using literature sources on Caucasian spiders (see list in Otto 2023) as well as Nentwig et al. (2023) and sources listed therein. For specimen identification, we used a Zeiss Stemi 508 Stereo Microscope with 8:1 Zoom and a Zeiss Apo 1.5x FWD 53 mm front lens attached. Photos of preserved specimens were taken using a Canon EOS 550D camera equipped with a Canon EF 100mm f/2.8 Macro USM lens. Digital images were prepared using Zerene Stacker image stacking software and Adobe Photoshop CS6. Drawings were made based on microscope photographs and using a Wacom CTH-690 Intuos Medium Pen and Touch Tablet with the programs Krita (version 2.9.7) and Photoshop CS6 (version 13.0). Drawings usually show the left male palp; perspective and scale bars are given in the plates and their captions. The preparation of the female epigyne and endogyne was done using a 30% solution of potassium hydroxide.

DNA processing

Genomic DNA was extracted from the sample tissue using the Quick-DNA Miniprep PlusKit (Zymo Research) (for 25 mg of tissue). Partial sequences of cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI) were amplified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using the primer pairs LCOI490-JJ and

HCO2198-JJ (Astrin and Stüben 2008). Thermal conditions included denaturation at 95°C for 1 min, followed by the first cycle set (15 cycles): 94°C for 30 sec, annealing at 55°C for 1 min (-1°C per cycle), and extension at 72°C for 1:30 min. Second cycle set (25 cycles): 94°C for 35 sec, 45°C for 1 min, 72°C for 1:30 min, followed by 1 cycle at 72°C for 3 min, and the final extension step at 72°C for 5 min. PCR amplicons were visualized on 1% agarose gels using $1.7\ \mu\text{l}$ of PCR product. Sequencing of the unpurified PCR products in both directions was conducted at the Beijing Genomics Institute (Hong Kong, CN) by using the amplification primers. Sequence analysis was performed using Geneious Prime 2022.1.1. (<http://www.geneious.com>). Extracted DNA was deposited in the scientific collections of Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia, while the sequences have been submitted to Barcode of Life Data Systems (BOLD) databases. The newly obtained DNA barcodes of COI sequences were checked against the BOLD Systems database (<http://www.boldsystems.org/index.php>). The Barcode Index Number (BIN) (Ratnasingham and Hebert 2013) for the sequenced taxa and their nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems (if they had a BIN) are also given. For the calculation of sequence differentiation, we used p -distance as performed in the BOLD Systems.

Results

In total, 1091 spiders (including 499 males, 555 females, and 37 juveniles) were collected during the sampling period, comprising 297 species from 179 genera and 33 families. The 100 species marked with an asterisk (*) listed below were recorded in Georgia for the first time; among them, 18 species marked with a double asterisk (**) represent the first records in the Caucasus. The list below is given in alphabetical order.

From the collected material submitted for the barcoding pipeline, 283 quality barcodes (500 – 658 bp length barcodes, with no stop codons, indels, or deletions) representing 150 species were generated so far, of which 48 barcodes (26 species) are the first ones to be submitted to the BOLD Systems. Barcode information is given under each barcoded species listed below.

Abbreviations used are as follows: **Mun.** – municipality; **R.** – river; **Vill.** – village; **MT** – Malaise trap; **NP** – National Park.

List of spider species recorded

Family Cheiracanthiidae Wagner, 1887

Cheiracanthium mildei L. Koch, 1864

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; meadow at Alazani R.; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010009 • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; MT; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 24 Apr. – 1 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012861 • 3♀; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; MT; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 1/14 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-Ids: 1021352, 1021353, 1021354.

Genetics. Two barcodes obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010009 and 1021352 (BOLD:AAB7601, maximum *p*-distance 2.13%) had the nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems as follows: for the CaBOL-ID 1010009 *C. mildei* from Canada (BOLD:AAB7601, 0.31% *p*-distance); for the CaBOL-ID 1021352 *C. mildei* from Bulgaria (BOLD:AAB7601, 1.34% *p*-distance).

Remarks. Species with an Eastern Palearctic distribution, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In Georgia, it was previously recorded from the Abkhazia region. It is the first record from the Kakheti region (Otto 2023).

***Cheiracanthium montanum* L. Koch, 1877**

GEORGIA – **Kvemo Kartli** • 1♂; Tetrtskaro Mun., S of Manglisi; N41.67732°, E44.38353°; 1074 m a.s.l.; montane meadow; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 414.

Remarks. Species with an Eastern Palearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In Georgia, the species is known from the Samachablo (Atriskhevi) and Kakheti (Lagodekhi NP) regions (Otto 2023). Here it is reported from the Kvemo Kartli region for the first time.

****Cheiracanthium pelasgicum* (C.L. Koch, 1837)**

GEORGIA – **Shida Kartli** • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9801°, E44.1907°; 611 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023920 (Figs 1–2).

Remarks. This palaeartic species is distributed from North Africa east to Tajikistan and north to EE Rusia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Armenia, Dagestan, and Russia (Stavropol Krai

(Otto 2023). Herein, it is reported from Georgia for the first time. *Cheiracanthium pelasgicum* mainly occurs in arid habitats, such as steppes and dry shrublands. The somatic characteristics and palp structure matched those of *C. pelasgicum* given in Nentwig et al. (2023).

Family Clubionidae Simon, 1878

***Clubiona alpicola* Kulczyński, 1882**

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 2♀♀, 1♂; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; in settlement, malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 22 Aug. – 4 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1021355, 1021356, 1021357.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1021356 and 1021357 (BOLD:AFH1071, maximum *p*-distance 0.61%). The identification via COI gene is not straightforward as the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems is *C. frutetorum* L. Koch, 1867 from Germany (BOLD:AAY8046, mean *p*-distance 4.54%).

Remarks. Palearctic species distributed from Germany to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). An abundant species distributed throughout the entire Caucasus. In Georgia, *C. alpicola* is known from numerous localities (Otto 2023).

***Clubiona caucasica* Mikhailov & Otto, 2017**

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 1♂, 1♀; Lagodekhi Mun., Lagodekhi NP; N41.8525°, E46.2878°; 670 m a.s.l.; mountain forest, malaise trap; leg. G. Japoshvili and G. Kirkitadze; 28 Jul. – 5 Aug. 2014; CaBOL-IDs 1004125, 1004126. **Adjara** • 2♀♀; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7294°,

Figures 1–6. *Cheiracanthium pelasgicum*, male (1: left palp, ventral view; 2: same, retrolateral view). *Clubiona phragmitis*, female (3: epigyne, ventral view; 4: endogyne, dorsal view). *Porrhoclubiona genevensis*, male (5: left palp, ventral view; 6: same, retrolateral view).

E42.0775°; 1020 m a.s.l.; woods at Khino monastery; leg. GGBC (CaBOL) team; 6 – 20 May 2018; CaBOL-IDs 1012734, 1012735.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012734 and 1012735 (BOLD:AAZ7986). This species is not present in BOLD Systems. Identification via COI barcode is not straightforward, as *C. caucasica* and its nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems, *C. caeruleascens* L. Koch, 1867 from Germany and Austria (BOLD:AAZ7986), have a mean difference (*p*-dist) of only 1.69%.

Remarks. The distribution of the species is restricted to the Caucasus and Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Clubiona golovatchi Mikhailov, 1990

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 1♂, 1♀; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; suburban area; MT; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 24 – 31 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012836, 1012859. **Imereti** • 1♂, 1♀; Chiatura Mun., Mandaeti Vill.; N43.3284°, E42.1756°; 770 m a.s.l.; suburban area, MT; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 23 May – 5 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012758, 1012759.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012758 and 1012759 (BOLD:AFH1498), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. frutetorum* from Finland (BOLD:AAY8046, mean *p*-distance 3.55%). There are no barcodes of *C. golovatchi* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. The species is reported from the Caucasus, Turkey, and Iran (Nentwig 2023). The data retrieved from the collected material corresponds well to the known range of *C. golovatchi* in Georgia (Otto 2023).

Clubiona lutescens Westring, 1851

GEORGIA – **Guria** • 1♀; Ozurgeti Mun., Zvani Vill., Natanebi R.; N41.9349°, E41.9876°; 67 m a.s.l.; in soil litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 9 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012774. **Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti** • 1♀; Tkibuli Mun., Nakerala Ridge; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 188.

Genetics. A single barcode obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012774 (BOLD:AEJ4828) matches *C. lutescens* from Canada (BOLD:AAO3476, *p*-distance 1.26%) in BOLD Systems.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (WSC 2023), distributed throughout the entire Caucasus.

Clubiona neglecta O. P. Cambridge, 1862

GEORGIA – **Kvemo Kartli** • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Kumi-si Vill.; N41.6009°, E44.8242°; 486 m a.s.l.; reed thicket; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016853. **Tbilisi** • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7697°, E44.7699°; 436 m a.s.l.; meadow, under bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Dec. 2021 (home reared from subadult); CaBOL-ID 1011128. **Mtskheta-Mtianeti** • 1♂, 1♀; Kazgebi Mun., S of Stepantsminda; N42.637°, E44.631°; 1745 m a.s.l.; leg. H.-J. Krammer and L. Karalashvili; 5 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TISs-8008082, 8008083.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016853 and 1011128 (BOLD:AAV9244, *p*-distance 0.46%), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. neglecta* from Slovenia (BOLD:AAV9244, mean *p*-distance 2.4%).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (WSC 2023), with numerous records from the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023).

Clubiona pallidula (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, on vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025666.

Remarks. This species has a transpalaeartic distribution (WSC 2023). In Georgia, it is known from Imereti, Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti, and Adjara, as well as from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from the Kakheti region.

**Clubiona phragmitis* C.L. Koch, 1843

GEORGIA – **Shida Kartli** • 1♀; Kaspi Mun., Kodistskaro Vill.; N42.01700°, E44.35120°; 715 m a.s.l.; floodplain, on *Arundo* sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012548 (Figs 3–4) • 1♀; N42.01700°, E44.35120°; 715 m a.s.l.; floodplain, on *Arundo* sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 26 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012549.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012548 and 1012549 (BOLD:ACE5367, *p*-distance 0.15%), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. phragmitis* from Germany (BOLD:ACE5367, maximum *p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

Clubiona pseudosimilis Mikhailov, 1990

GEORGIA – **Samtskhe-Javakheti** • 2♀♀; Baghdati Mun., Zekari Pass; N41.8522°, E42.8078°; 2197 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, sweeping; leg. E. Arsenashvili; 11 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032332, 1032333.

Remarks. This species has a disjunct Eastern Palaearctic distribution, known from Algeria, Portugal, Crete, Turkey, and the entire Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). The holotype of *C. pseudosimilis* was described from Lagodekhi NP at 2100 m a.s.l. (Mikhailov 1990). In Georgia, this species is mainly distributed along the Greater Caucasus, with a single record in the Lesser Caucasus from Bakuriani (Otto 2023).

**Porrhoclubiona genevensis* (L. Koch, 1866)

GEORGIA – **Tbilisi** • 2♂♂, 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7819°, E44.6998°; 732 m a.s.l.; ravine in *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, *Carpinus* sp. leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 12 Dec. 2021 (home-reared (1011211) adult on 26 Jan. 2022 and another (1020754) adult on 13 Jan. 2022); CaBOL-IDs 1011211, 1020717,

1020754 • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8000°, E44.6824°; 874 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021066 (Figs 5–6) • 1♀ (subad); Dig-homi Park; N41.7681°, E44.7717°; 413 m a.s.l.; leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032347.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Iberian Peninsula north to the Scandinavian Peninsula and east to South Siberia and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously recorded from Azerbaijan and Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. genevensis* from Georgia. The copulatory organs, as well as somatic characteristics, matched those of *P. genevensis* given by Bosmans et al. (2017) and Nentwig et al. (2023).

Family Cybaeidae Banks, 1892

Cybaeus abchasicus Charitonov, 1947

GEORGIA – **Adjara** • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67495°, E41.87580°; 300 m a.s.l.; Chakvistiskali R., under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2010; KVS 336; CaBOL-ID 1004140 • 1♂; Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 1700 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 7 – 8 Sep. 2018; KVS 518.

Remarks. Endemic to the Western Caucasus, where it is known from 7 localities in Abkhazia and adjacent Krasnodar Krai. The species was described based on the juvenile specimen. Brignoli (1978) described a female from Artvin Province, Turkey, thought to belong to the same species. Most likely, the record from Turkey (Brignoli 1978) refers to another species.

Family Dictynidae O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

Argyroneta aquatica (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – **Samtskhe-Javakheti** • 1♂; Aspindza Mun., Tsundi Lake; N41.41113°, E43.32790°; 1235 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Arsenashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018149.

Remarks. This species has a very broad Palaearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). Known from several localities in Georgia (Otto 2023), *A. aquatica* has always been a real challenge for arachnologists due to its fully submerged lifestyle. The Tsundi Lake is the southernmost record from the Caucasus region.

Dictyna ottoi Marusik & Koponen, 2017

GEORGIA – **Guria** • 1♂, 1♀; Ozurgeti Mun., Gaghma Dvabzu Vill.; N41.9466°, E42.0648°; 126 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 May 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020798, 1020799. **Shida Kartli** • 1♂; Gori; N41.9770°, E44.0966°; 590 m a.s.l.; steppe vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 9 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023882. **Kakheti** • 1♂; Telavi; N41.9141°, E45.4588°; 801 m a.s.l.; suburban area; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025796.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020799 and 1023882 (BOLD:AAO1632). This species is not present in BOLD

Systems at the time, as we submit the first COI sequence for this taxon.

Remarks. This species is restricted to the Caucasus region and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). Within the country, *D. ottoi* has been previously reported from Lagodekhi (Otto and Japoshvili 2018). With *D. uncinata* Thorell, 1856 it belongs to the *uncinata*-species group. According to Marusik and Koponen (2017), old records of *D. armata* Thorell, 1875 from Georgia and the Caucasus overall should be ascribed to its sibling species, *D. ottoi*, since no illustrations have been provided by the authors.

Lathys humilis (Blackwall, 1855)

GEORGIA – **Tbilisi** • 1♂ (subadult); Tbilisi; N44.7798°, E41.7195°; 440 m a.s.l.; suburban area, malaisetraps; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 11. – 25 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021359. **Kakheti** • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Artsivis Kheoba (Eagle Gorge); N41.4900°, E46.0975°; 754 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023778 • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., NW of Akhmeta, Aniskhevi R.; N42.0830°, E45.3004°; 1022 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. CaBOL team; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031229.

Genetics. A single barcode obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1021359 (BOLD:) was identical to *L. humilis* from Canada (BOLD:AAU0840) and nearly identical to several specimens from Germany and Netherlands (BOLD:AAU0840, 0.15% *p*-distance).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is a common species throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023). It is the second record of this species from Georgia, previously reported from Lagodekhi NP (Otto and Japoshvili 2018).

**Lathys spasskyi* Andreeva & Tystshenko, 1969

GEORGIA – **Samtskhe-Javakheti** • 2♂♂, 1♀ (subadult); Aspindza Mun., above Vardzia; N41.38793°, E43.27602°; 1800 m a.s.l.; subalpine south-exposed meadow, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 6 Apr. 2009; KBS 198a; CaBOL-ID 1004142. **Shida Kartli** • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki ridge; N41.9833°, E44.1495°; 642 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 4 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035451 (Fig. 7).

Remarks. This species is distributed from Bulgaria east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is the first record of *L. spasskyi* from Georgia and the second for the Caucasus after it was previously reported from Azerbaijan (Marusik et al. 2004, 2015). Until Marusik et al. (2015) this species has been treated as a junior synonym of *L. stigmatistata* (Menge, 1869) for a long time.

Nigma flavescens (Walckenaer, 1830)

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 2♂♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; Alazani R., on *Tamarix* sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023348, 1023757 • 1♀, 2♂♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature

Figures 7–9. *Lathys spasskyi*, female (7: endogyne, dorsal view). *Nigma walckenaeri*, male (8: left palp, ventral view; 9: same, retrolateral view).

Reserve; N42.2223°, E45.3032°; 805 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, meadow; leg. Cabol team; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1031241, 1031242, 1031243. **Tbilisi** • 2♂♂; Krtsanisi Park; N41.6216°, E44.9341°; 355 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, on vegetation; leg. G. Iankoshvili; 29 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023867, 1023868.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from North Africa east to Iran and north to Central Europe (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In Georgia, it was previously recorded from Atsriskhevi and Lagodekhi NP (Otto 2023). The specimens from Mijniskure (Vashlovani NP) extend the known distribution within the country to its extreme southeast. It is the first record from Tbilisi. *Nigma flavescens* could be found on shrubs and bushes while overwintering in leaf litter.

****Nigma walckenaeri* (Roewer, 1951)**

GEORGIA – **Shida Kartli** • 2♂♂, 1♀; Gori; N41.97544°, E44.10496°; 590 m a.s.l.; montane, on *Hedera* sp; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Jul. 2019; CaBOL-ID 1004145 (Figs 8–9), 1004146, 1004147 • 1♀; N41.96743°, E44.09838°; 849 m a.s.l.; forest, on *Hedera* sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 23 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018741.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004145 and 1018741 (BOLD:AFH3905, *p*-distance 0.65%), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *N. walckenaeri* from the Netherlands (BOLD:ABY1639, mean *p*-distance 2.39%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from North Africa to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously reported from Azerbaijan and Adygea (Otto 2023). It is the first record in Georgia.

Family Dysderidae C.L. Koch, 1837

***Cryptoparachtes adzharius* Dunin, 1992**

GEORGIA – **Adjara** • 1♀; Kintrishi NP; N41.7334°, E42.0244°; 440 m a.s.l.; montane *Alnus* forest, rock slide/pile; leg. S. Otto; 3 Jun. 2009; CaBOL-ID 1004148.

Remarks. This is by far the smallest *Cryptoparachtes* species (Dunin 1992), known only by several specimens, with distribution restricted to the southwestern part of Georgia. Although there are no findings of *C. adzharius* outside Georgia and the genus itself is endemic to the Caucasus (WSC 2023), its occurrence in the adjacent parts of Turkey is highly likely.

***Cryptoparachtes fedotovi* (Charitonov, 1956)**

GEORGIA – **Kakheti** • 2♀♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks/rotten logs; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025654, 1025655 • 1♀; Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025670.

Remarks. Along with *C. charitonowi* (Mcheidze, 1972), *C. fedotovi* inhabits the broad-leaved forests of Eastern Georgia (Otto 2023). The known elevation range of *C. fedotovi* is within 500–1000 m. (Dunin 1992), specimen CaBOL-ID 1025670 not only extends its elevation of occurrence to > 1900 m a.s.l., but it was also found in an unusual habitat – a subalpine meadow with no sight of forest nearby. No males of this species are known, as we also failed to find one. After analyzing the temporal data of captured females (Dunin

1992; current study), males should be mainly searched from the end of March to the end of April.

Dysdera dunini Deeleman-Reinhold, 1988

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Senaki Mun., SE of Senaki; N42.26500°, E42.08583°; 20 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 25 Sep. 2011; KVS 312.

Remarks. The species is known from the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023), southern Ukraine, and Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Dysdera gmelini Dunin, 1991

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7712°, E44.7654°; 446 m a.s.l.; artificial pine forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 26 Mar. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009767.

Remarks. This species was described from Georgia (Algeti NP) (Dunin 1991). Here we report the second record of this endemic species from Georgia and the Caucasus. The female of this species remains unknown.

Dysdera inopinata Dunin, 1991

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Kiketi; N41.6452°, E44.6402°; 1186 m a.s.l.; mixed broad-leaved forest, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 6 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010059.

Remarks. This species was described from Georgia (Magalakhari Pass) (Dunin 1991). Here we report the second record of this endemic species from Georgia and the Caucasus. The female of this species remains unknown.

Harpactea caucasica (Kulczyński, 1895)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♀♀; Lagodekhi Mun., Lagodekhi N.P.; N41.85734°, E46.30479°; 700 m a.s.l.; beech forest, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 30 Mar. 2009; KBS 192. **Mtskheta-Mtianeti** • 1♂, 2♀♀; Giorgitsminda; N42.6286°, E45.1259°; 1600 m a.s.l.; montane slate slide, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 24 Jun. 2009; KVS 220; CaBOL-IDs 1004153, 1004154, 1004155.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus (WSC 2023).

Harpactea logunovi Dunin, 1992

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027706.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus, recorded in Georgia and N Caucasus (Otto 2023).

**Harpactea modesta* Dunin, 1991

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Kaspi Mun., Nichbisi Vill.; N41.8426°, E44.5310°; 700 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks and leaf litter; leg. Cabol team; 30 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032340 (Figs 10–11).

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus, previously recorded in Azerbaijan and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *H. modesta* in Georgia.

Harpactea paradoxa Dunin, 1992

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♂♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025709, 1031224.

Remarks. This species is endemic to Georgia. The examined material corresponds to a previously known distribution pattern (Dunin 1992), as this species range remains restricted to the area between Tsiv-Gombori Range and Batsara-Babaneuri Protected Area (Otto 2023).

Harpactea spasskyi Dunin, 1992

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 1♀; Kiketi; N41.6412°, E44.6389°; 1177 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 26 Mar. 2023.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Georgia and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is also reported from Ukraine (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Family Eresidae C.L. Koch, 1845

Eresus sp. (*sandalitatus*-species group)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 2♂♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9872°, E44.1320°; 681 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023296, 1023801 • 2♂♂; Gori; N41.9674°, E44.0984°; 849 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; 23 Oct. 2021; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; CaBOL-IDs 1018700, 1018701. Tbilisi • 1♂; Didgori Vill.; N41.78104°, E44.67459°; 850 m a.s.l.; south-exposed slope near ravine with oak forest; 25 Sep. 2020; leg. A. Seropian; CaBOL-ID 1004222

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs, 1004222, 1018700, 1018701 (BOLD:AFH0787) and 102381 (BOLD:AFH1488) (mean *p*-distance 2.3%) with the three nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems as follows: CaBOL-ID 1004222 to *Eresus* sp. 2 KS-2021a from Iran (BOLD:AEK1496, *p*-distance 2.3%), *Eresus* sp. F KS-2021a from Turkey (BOLD:AEE6991, *p*-distance 2.46%) and *E. kollari* from Bulgaria with a Private status (*p*-distance 2.46%); CaBOL-IDs 108700 and 1018701 to *Eresus* sp. 2 KS-2021a from Iran (BOLD:AEK1496, *p*-distance 2.54%), *Eresus* sp. F KS-2021a from Turkey (BOLD:AEE6991, *p*-distance 2.61%) and *E. kollari* from Bulgaria with a Private status (*p*-distance 2.75%); CaBOL-ID 10238101 to *Eresus* sp. F KS-2021a from Turkey (BOLD:AEE6991, *p*-distance 2.46%), *E. hermani* from Hungary (BOLD:AES6096, *p*-distance 2.76%) and *Eresus* sp. 2 KS-2021a from Iran (BOLD:AEK1496, *p*-distance 2.92%).

Remarks. Neither the determination via obtained sequences was straightforward, nor did the examination of genitalia help with solving the case (see Supplementary File). As a result of studies conducted in Central Europe on the *E. sandalitatus* species group (to which *E. sandalitatus*, *E. moravicus*, *E. hermani*, and *E. kollari* belong) over the past two decades, two cryptic species have been described (Řežáč et al. 2008; Kovács et al. 2015) that differ both in phenological features and in small differences of the copulatory organs of both sexes. Given the lack of any diagnostic draw-

Figures 10–11. *Harpactea modesta*, male (10: left palp, retrolateral view; 11: same, prolateral view).

ings of *E. kollari* males previously collected in the Caucasus (the drawing provided by Mcheidze (1997) was actually redrawn from Azheganova (1968)), further targeted studies of more material based on an integrative approach may reveal the potentially hidden diversity of local *Eresus* sp.

****Stegodyphus lineatus* (Latreille, 1817)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♂♂; Vashlovani NP, Mijniskure; N41.1127°, E46.6461°; 101 m a.s.l.; semidesert; J.P. Kaitila and J. Junnilainen; 22 May 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035778 (Figs 12–13), 1035792.

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Mediterranean east to Tajikistan (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, *S. lineatus* was previously recorded in Azerbaijan and Armenia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

Filistatidae

***Pritha pallida* (Kulczyński, 1897)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7242°, E44.7288°; 513 m a.s.l.; building wall; leg. L.-G. Japaridze, 12 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010278 • 1♀; N41.7574°, E44.7790°; 427 m a.s.l.; wall crevices; leg. A. Seropian; 7 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010280 • 2♀♀; N41.7574°, E44.7790°; 427 m a.s.l.; wall crevices; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 20 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012595, 1012628. Kakheti • 1♀; Telavi Mun., Telavi; N41.9201°, E45.4743°; 726 m a.s.l.; wall; leg. A. Zukakishvili; 8 Sep. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032344.

Remarks. *Pritha pallida* has a disjunctive Caucasus-Mediterranean range (Nentwig et al. 2023). Marusik et al. (2019) reported this species from Georgia (Tbilisi) and the overall Caucasus for the first time. The record from Telavi extends its known distribution within the country, 60 km NW. In addition, two photo of *P. pallida* females from Ushguli and Gaghma Dvabzu Villages can be found in the Georgian Biodiversity Database (Tarkhnishvili et al. 2013), pointing to a much wider distribution of this species within the country's territory.

Family Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892

****Anagraphis pallens* Simon, 1893**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Pantishara Gorge; N41.1518°, E46.5755°; 261 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023770 • 1♀; Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir (Chachuna Managed Reserve); N41.2769°, E45.8887°; 237 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 19 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026480 (Figs 14–15). Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.778°, E44.701°; 739 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian, E. Karalashvili, H.-J. Krammer; 17 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TIS-8008319. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂, 1♀; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681°, E44.8219°; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020864 (Supplementary File), 1020865.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023770 (BOLD:AFH2123). There are no barcodes of *A. pallens* available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. This species is distributed from the eastern Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was reported from Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Aphantaulax trifasciata* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, thorn shrubs; leg. S. Otto; 13 Aug. 2007; KVS 270.

Remarks. This species has a Transpalearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). Distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia). It is the second and the southeasternmost record of this species within Georgia (Otto 2023).

Figures 12–13. *Stegodyphus lineatus*, male (12: preserved specimen from Vashlovani NP; 13: left palp, ventral view).

Figures 14–17. *Anagraphis pallens*, female (14: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 15: endogyne, dorsal view). *Callilepis nocturna*, female (16: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 17: endogyne, dorsal view).

****Callilepis nocturna* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Tetrtskaro Mun., Akhali Zirbiti Vill.; N41.6562°, E44.5644°; 1337 m a.s.l.; meadow, on vegetation; leg. G. Iankoshvili; 9 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1004252 (Figs 16–17). Tbilisi • 1♀ (juv.); Telovani Vill.; N41.8000°, E44.5644°; 874 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter, forest edge; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021075.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1004252 (BOLD:AFH4118) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. nocturna* from Norway (BOLD:AAZ8977, *p*-distance 3.37%).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously reported from Armenia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *C. nocturna* from Georgia.

***Civizelotes caucasicus* (L. Koch, 1866)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7812°, E44.6978°; 785 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027283, 1027284. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kodistskaro; N42.0292°, E44.3489°; 774 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1028019. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681°, E44.8219°; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020857.

Genetics. Three nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1028019, 1027283, and 1027284 (BOLD:AFD7370, *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. caucasicus* from Bulgaria with an Early-Release status (mean *p*-distance 3.17%).

Remarks. *Civizelotes caucasicus* is known from most of the Mediterranean and Black Sea countries, the European part of Russia, Central Asia, China (Nentwig et al. 2023), and the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023).

***Drassodes pubescens* (Thorell, 1856)**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 1700 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 7. – 8 Sep. 2018; KVS 520. Kakheti • 1♀, 2♂♂; Akhmeta Mun., Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025749, 1025750, 1025751. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Akhalkalaki Mun., Bozali Vill.; N41.2714°, E43.3379°; 1866 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 6 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025761.

Genetics. Three barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1025749, 1025750 (BOLD:AFH0179), and 1025761 (BOLD:AFH0862) (mean *p*-distance 0.96%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *D. pubescens* from Germany (BOLD:AAO0670, mean *p*-distance 2.18%).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023), previously reported in the Caucasus from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *D. pubescens* from the Adjara and

Samtskhe-Javakheti regions respectively. In Georgia, it was known from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Abkhazia regions, as well as from Tbilisi (Otto 2023).

***Drassyllus pusillus* (C.L. Koch, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Tsalka Mun., S of Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; Artemisia grassland; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 418.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023), very abundant in the Caucasus (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it was previously reported from several localities in the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Gnaphosa lucifuga* (Walckenaer, 1802)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9870°, E44.1562°; 667 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, soil crevices; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023820 • 1♀; N41.9870°, E44.1562°; 667 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi shrubland, soil crevices; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025512 • 1♀; N41.9870°, E44.1562°; 667 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi shrubland, soil crevices; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027339.

Genetics. Two barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1023820 and 1027339 (BOLD:AFH0315, *p*-distance 1.37%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *G. lucifuga* from Germany (BOLD:ABA7163, mean *p*-distance 2.98%).

Remarks. The species has a wide Palaearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is distributed throughout the whole Caucasus. In Georgia, it was reported from the Abkhazia, Adjara, Guria, Samtskhe-Javakheti, Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti, and Tusheti regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from the Shida Kartli region. Studied material was caught in an abandoned trench. The spider's presence was determined by the presence or absence of webbing with a bluish tinge on the trench wall cracks.

***Gnaphosa lugubris* (C.L. Koch, 1839)**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Tetrtskaro Mun., S of Manglisi; N41.6773°, E44.3835°; 1100 m a.s.l.; montane meadow; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; CaBOL-ID 1004170. Kakheti region • 2♀♀; Akhmeta Mun., Girevi Vill.; N42.4951°, E45.4816°; 2000 m a.s.l.; rock scree near R.; leg. F. Walther; 6 Sep. 2009; CaBOL-IDs 1004171, 1004172.

Remarks. The species is widespread in Europe, the Caucasus (except for Armenia), and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). The present findings fit well within the known distribution of this species in Georgia (Otto 2023).

****Gnaphosa steppica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7812°, E44.6978°; 785 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID

1027285 • 1♂; N41.7786°, E44.7073°; 642 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035449 (Figs 20–21). Shida Kartli region • 2♀♀; Kaspi Mun., Kodistskaro; N42.0292°, E44.3489°; 774 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027994 (Figs 18–19), 1027995.

Genetics. Three identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1027285, 1027994, and 1027995 (BOLD:AFC3075) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *G. steppica* from Russia with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 3.86%).

Remarks. In the Caucasus, the species was reported from Azerbaijan and the N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *G. steppica* from Georgia. It is also known from Ukraine, Turkey, Central Asia, and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WCS 2023).

*****Haplodrassus orientalis* (L. Koch, 1866)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9872°, E44.1499°; 716 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Nov. 2021;

CaBOL-ID 1020800 (Figs 22–23). Tbilisi • 1♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7841°, E44.6812°; 816 m a.s.l.; pasture, under rock, freshly molted; leg. A. Seropian; 21 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011136 • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7810°, E44.6970°; 786 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 22 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035461.

Remarks. This is the first record of this species from Georgia and the whole Caucasus. Both specimens were found in sunny and dry habitats. The nearest reports of *H. orientalis* are from South Russia, Ukraine, and Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Haplodrassus signifer* (C.L. Koch, 1839)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., vicinity of David Gareja Monastery; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KBS 204 • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP; N41.139°, E44.5808°; 213 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock near Lekistkali (Mlashedskali) R.; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010011. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Tsalka Mun., S of

Figures 18–21. *Gnaphosa steppica*, female (18: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 19: endogyne, dorsal view), male (20: left palp, ventral view; 21: same, retrolateral view).

Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; Artemisia grassland; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KBS 216 • 1♂; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3561°, E43.2547°; 1260 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 7 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035460. Kvemo Kartli region • 1♂; Tetrtskaro Mun., S of Manglisi; N41.67732°, E44.38353°; 1074 m a.s.l.; montane meadow; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 415.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010011 (BOLD:AAL7077) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. signifer* from Germany (BOLD:ADL9712, *p*-distance 2.6%).

Remarks. Species with a Holarctic distribution (WSC 2023). It is very abundant and widely distributed throughout the Caucasus (Otto 2023).

****Haplodrassus silvestris* (Blackwall, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8009°, E44.6807°; 888 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 02 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1023281 (Figs 24–25).

Genetics. We obtained a single barcode from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023281 (BOLD:AFG9937) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. silvestris* from Austria with a Private status (*p*-distance 4.28%). The sec-

ond-best match is another *H. silvestris* from Slovenia (BOLD:AAO2338, *p*-distance 4.43%).

Remarks. In the Caucasus, the species was earlier known from Azerbaijan and the N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia. *Haplodrassus silvestris* has a broad European distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023).

***Kishidaia conspicua* (L. Koch, 1866)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., Sabue Vill.; N42.0566°, E45.1232°; 635 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. B. Chitadze; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031227.

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed from Spain to the Far East of Russia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was recorded in all countries except for Armenia. The specimen from Sabue Village is the first record in the Kakheti region, as previous country records from Georgia originate from the Samachablo and Abkhazia regions (Otto 2023).

***Micaria formicaria* (Sundevall, 1831)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9703°, E44.9774°; 982 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Jul. 2021; CaBOL ID-1011782. Mtskhe-

Figures 22–25. *Haplodrassus orientalis*, female (22: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 23: endogyne, dorsal view). *Haplodrassus silvestris*, female (24: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 25: endogyne, dorsal view).

ta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Dusheti Mun., W of Giorgitsminda Vill.; N42.6379°, E45.0989°; 2000 m a.s.l.; montane meadow, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 2 Aug. 2027; CaBOL-ID 1004173.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011782 (BOLD:ABU7150) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. formicaria* from the Czech Republic (BOLD:ABU7150, *p*-distance 0.62%).

Remarks. Species with a disjunct Caucaso-Far Eastern distribution (Marusik et al. 2005). Abundant species, widely distributed throughout the Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *M. formicaria* in Georgia from the Shida Kartli region, as the previous country reports originate from the Kakheti and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023).

Micaria pulicaria (Sundevall, 1831)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Kojori; N41.67450°, E44.69962°; 1400 m a.s.l.; xerothermic shrubland near pines; leg. S. Otto; 12 May 2009; KBS 205. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region • 2♀♀; Martvili Mun., Lebarde; N42.7382°, E42.5006°; 1625 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027131, 1027132.

Remarks. This species has a transpalearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is widely distributed throughout the Caucasus (Otto 2023) and the whole Palaearctic (WSC 2023). In Georgia, the species is known from Oni (Otto 2023). This is the second record of *M. pulicaria* from the country and the first from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region and Tbilisi.

Micaria silesiaca L. Koch, 1875

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂, 2♀♀(subadult); Akhmeta Mun., Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; sub-alpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025675, 1025690, 1025701.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, the species is reported from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Russia (North Ossetia-Alania). It is the second record of *M. silesiaca* in Georgia and the first from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region, as the previous country record originates from the Kakheti region (Otto 2023).

***Micaria subopaca* Westring, 1861

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.7670°, E44.7729°; 430 m a.s.l.; Quercus sp. bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 25 Feb. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035475 (Figs 26–27).

Remarks. It is the first record in Georgia and the entire Caucasus region of this otherwise widely distributed species in Europe (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Nomisia ausseveri (L. Koch, 1872)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Sagarejo, N41.63850°, E45.35780°; 750 m a.s.l.; pasture, in grass; leg. S. Otto; 13 Aug. 2007; CaBOL-ID 1004174. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3529°, E43.2518°; 1315

Figures 26–31. *Micaria subopaca*, male (26: left palp, retrolateral view; 27: same, ventral view). *Iberina montana*, male (28: left palp, ventral view; 29: same, retrolateral view), female (30: endogyne, dorsal view). *Mastigusa arietina*, female (31: epigyne, prepared, ventral view).

m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032746.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Mediterranean to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, the species is reported from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. It is the second record of *N. aussereri* from Georgia and the first from the Kakheti and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions (Otto 2023).

Nomisia conigera (Spassky, 1941)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Pantishara Gorge; N41.1518°, E46.5755°; 261 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023794 • 2♀♀; Chachuna Managed Reserve; N41.220470°, E45.972396°; 242 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. E. Arsenashvili; 20 May 2023.

Genetics. There are no barcodes of this species available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023794 (BOLD:AAV1581) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *Nomisia* sp. from Turkey with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 1.83%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, known from Turkey, the Caucasus, Iran, and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously recorded from Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first report of *N. conigera* from the Kakheti region.

Nomisia exornata (C.L. Koch, 1839)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681°, E44.8219°; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020885.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed in Europe, North Africa, Turkey, Caucasus, and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia). In Georgia, it was recorded in the Samachablo region and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *N. exornata* from the Kvemo Kartli region.

Poecilochroa variana (C.L. Koch, 1839)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1juv; Gori; N41.9795°, E44.0941°; 584 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under log; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, 31 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011621 • 1♀; N41.97960°, E44.09410°; 584 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012439 Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Kazbegi Mun., Stepantsminda; 42.653°N, 44.655°E, 1867 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 2 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TIS-8008087 • 1♂; NW of Stepantsminda; 42.671°N, 44.61°E; 2008 m a.s.l.; leg. Wipfler B.; 7 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TIS-8008609.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012439 (BOLD:AAU2912) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. variana* from Turkey with Private status (*p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from Europe to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In Georgia,

this species was reported from the Samachablo region (Otto 2023). It is the second record from the country and the first from the Shida Kartli region.

Scotophaeus scutulatus (L. Koch, 1866)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9693°, E44.0948°; 932 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018731. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Borjomi Mun., Nedzvi Managed Reserve; N41.9010°, E43.5157°; 902 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest, under bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032754.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018731 (BOLD:AAO2286) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *S. scutulatus* from Germany (BOLD:AAO2286, *p*-distance 0.46%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from North Africa east to Central Asia and north to Sweden (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, the species is reported from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. It is the first record of *S. scutulatus* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region (Otto 2023).

Trachyzelotes pedestris (C.L. Koch, 1837)

GEORGIA • 1♀; Shida Kartli region, SW of Gori, Qvelaantubani Vill.; N41.85348°, E43.86911°; 1300 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 16 Sep. 2011; KVS 311.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Iberian Peninsula north to the Scandivian Peninsula and east to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously reported from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. It is the first record of *T. pedestris* from the Shida Kartli region (Otto 2023).

Urozelotes rusticus (L. Koch, 1872)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7574°, E44.7790°; 427 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 22 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025479. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro; N41.4641°, E46.0951°; 794 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025774.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, introduced to North and South Americas, Australia, and South Africa (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, the species is reported from Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. It is the first record of *U. rusticus* from the Kakheti region (Otto 2023).

**Zelotes hermani* (Chyzer, 1897)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; N-slope of rock formation, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 29 Mar. 2009; KVS 359.

Remarks. This species is distributed from Italy to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was known earlier from N Caucasus only. It is the first record of *Z. hermani* in Georgia and the South Caucasus (Otto 2023).

***Zelotes khostensis* Kovblyuk & Ponomarev, 2008**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 1700 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 8 Sep. 2018; KVS 519.

Remarks. This species has a disjunct Palaearctic distribution (Italy, Caucasus, and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023)). In the Caucasus, this species is generally distributed in N Caucasus with several records originating from Georgia (Samachablo and Abkhazia regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Z. khostensis* from the Adjara.

Family Hahniidae Bertkau, 1878***Habnia nava* (Blackwall, 1841)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Tsalka Mun., S of Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; Artemisia grassland, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 419. – Shida Kartli region • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9848°, E44.1389°; 636 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018732 • 1♀; N41.9956°, E44.1512°; 783 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020256. Kakheti • 1♀; Kvareli Mun., Sabue Vill.; N42.0566°, E45.1232°; 635 m a.s.l.; leg. Cabol team; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031238.

Remarks. *Habnia nava* is a species with a transpalearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in the NW Caucasus with several records originating from Georgia (Samachablo and Abkhazia regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *H. nava* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti, Shida Kartli, and Kakheti regions.

*****Iberina montana* (Blackwall, 1841)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 1♀, 3juv; Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 799 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020763 (Figs 28–29), 1020764 (Fig. 30), 1020765, 1020766, 1020767 • 1♀; N41.7848°, E44.6757°; 796 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021043.

Remarks. The species distribution ranges from Spain to western Russia and Turkey. It is the first record from Georgia and the whole Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). *Iberina montana* is a minuscule spider that can be easily confused with Linyphiidae by the naked eye.

****Mastigusa arietina* (Thorell, 1871)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7689°, E44.7719°; 430 m a.s.l.; meadow, under log; leg. A. Seropian and N. Bulbulashvili; 25 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035474 (Fig. 31).

Remarks: Distributed from the Mediterranean north to the Scandinavia Peninsula and east to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species previously

was recorded in Russia (North Ossetia). It is the first record from Georgia (Otto 2023).

***Mastigusa macrophthalma* (Kulczyński, 1897)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8103°, E44.6954°; 921 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under dead wood bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020243, 1020244 • 1♂; N41.8022°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021023 • 1♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7810°, E44.6746°; 850 m a.s.l.; dry ravine with oak forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 3 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1004220.

Remarks: This species has a disjunct Palaearctic distribution, known from the SC Europe, Balkans, and the Caucasus. In the Caucasus, this species is recorded only from Georgia (Otto 2023).

Family Linyphiidae Blackwall, 1859****Acartauchenius scurrilis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9956°, E44.1512°; 783 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020286 • 2♂♂; Gori; N41.9820°, E44.0879°; 586 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020784, 1020785 • 1♀; N41.9820°, E44.0879°; 586 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021001 • 1♀, 4♂♂; N41.9752°, E44.1044°; 583 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020792, 1020781, 1020793 (Figs 32–33), 1020794, 1020795.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020286 (BOLD:AET7303) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. scurrilis* from Bulgaria with Private status (*p*-distance 1.24%).

Remarks. *Acartauchenius scurrilis* has a wide Palaearctic distribution ranging from Spain north to the Scandinavian Peninsula and east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was known only from North Ossetia–Alania (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. scurrilis* from Georgia and the South Caucasus.

***Agyneta conigera* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1863)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Mamzvara Vill.; N41.2949°, E43.5334°; 1897 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 5 Jul. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012754.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed in Europe, the Far East of Russia, the Caucasus, Iran, and Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it was known only from the Abkhazia region. It is the first record of *A. conigera* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

Figures 32–37. *Acartauchenius scurrilis*, male (32: left palp, retrolateral view; 33: tibial apophysis, dorsal view). *Baryphyma proclive*, male (34: prosoma, lateral view; 35: same, dorsal view; 36: left palp, retrolateral view; 37: tibial apophysis, dorsal view).

Agyneta rurestris (C.L. Koch, 1836)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Tsalka Mun., S of Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; Artemisia grassland, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KBS 216. Imereti region • 1♂; Tkibuli Mun., Nakerala Pass; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest, on branches; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KVS 343. Tbilisi • 2♀♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8103°, E44.6954°; 921 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020283, 1020289.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020283 and 1020289 (BOLD:AAE5234) were identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. rurestris* from Germany (BOLD:AAE5234).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in all countries (Otto 2023). In Georgia, *A. rurestris* was previously reported only from the Abkhazia region. It is the first record of the species in Tbilisi, Samtskhe-Javakheti, and Imereti regions.

Araeoncus caucasicus Tanasevitch, 1987

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂, 1♀; Gori; N41.9771°, E44.1010°; 592 m a.s.l.; floodplain, Mtkvari R. bank, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1026323, 1026324. Tbilisi • 1♀; Vere Valley; N41.71609°,

E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 13 May 2009; KBS 206.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1026324 (BOLD:AFH1575). There are no barcodes of this species available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. Distributed from Ukraine east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in all countries (Otto 2023). In Georgia, *A. caucasicus* was previously reported only from the Abkhazia region. It is the first record of the species in the Shida Kartli region and Tbilisi.

Asthenargus caucasicus Tanasevitch, 1987

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♀♀, 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; 628 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, ravine, Carpinus orientalis leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020723, 1020724, 1020753 • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8016°, E44.6789°; 913 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, in Carpinus orientalis leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Jan. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1020780 • 3♀♀, 1♂; N41.8000°, E44.6824°; 847 m a.s.l.; meadow, in leaf litter at the forest edge; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1021068, 1021069, 1021070, 1021071.

Remarks. Species endemic to the Caucasus. It was described from Stepantsminda (Tanasevitch 1987), and it is the second record of *A. caucasicus* from Georgia (Otto 2023).

*****Baryphyma proclive* (Simon, 1884)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9956°, E44.1512°; 783 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020307 (Figs 34–37).

Remarks. It is the first time *Baryphyma* Simon, 1884 is reported in Georgia and *B. proclive* in the whole Caucasus. It's also the first record of this species outside of Italy after it was described from Rome (Simon 1884), extending its distribution 2600 km East.

***Bolyphantes alticeps* (Sundevall, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♀♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Poka Vill.; N41.3742°, E43.7731°; 2125 m a.s.l.; leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 9 Nov. 2018; CaBOL-IDs 1012756, 1012757 • 2♀♀; Akhalkalaki Mun., Tetrobi Managed Reserve; N41.5631°, E43.3533°; 1924 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032049, 1032050.

Genetics. A single barcode obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012757 (BOLD:ADD2365) was nearly identical to the COI gene of *B. alticeps* from Finland (BOLD:ADD2365, *p*-distance 0.92%).

Remarks. Transpalearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in all countries. In Georgia, *B. alticeps* was previously reported only from the Kakheti region (Lagodekhi NP) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Centromerita concinna* (Thorell, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Imereti region • 4♀♀; Baghdati Mun., Zekari Pass; N41.8522°, E42.8080°; 2196 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032030, 1032031, 1032736, 1032737.

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed in Europe and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded from Georgia and N Caucasus. In Georgia, it was previously reported only from the Samachablo region (Mamisoni Pass) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *C. concinna* from the Imereti region.

***Centromerus minor* Tanasevitch, 1990**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 3♀♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7820°, E44.7000°; 732 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011142, 1011143, 1011144, 1011141 • 3♂♂, 2♀♀; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; 628 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, ravine, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020773, 1020774, 1020775, 1020776, 1020777 • 1♂, 4♀♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 799 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020737, 1020738, 1020739, 1020740, 1020741.

Genetics. Three nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011143,

1020776, and 1020777 (BOLD:AAO0318, mean *p*-distance 0.63%), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. minor* from Turkey (Artvin) with Private status (mean *p*-distance 0.36%).

Remarks. A very abundant species widely distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023), also occurring in Iran and Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023). Tanasevitch (1990) indicates that this species belongs to the *C. sylvaticus* species group; however, unlike the latter, *C. minor* is characterized by reverse sexual dimorphism (RSD), i.e. males are larger than females. The material studied within the CaBOL project confirms the presence of RSD in *C. minor* (mean body length of a male – 1.83 mm; mean body length of a female – 1.64 mm).

***Centromerus sylvaticus* (Blackwall, 1841)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♂♂, 4♀♀; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.36000°, E43.71072°; 2223 m a.s.l.; forest; leg. L. Mumladze; 28 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-IDs 1012738, 1012739, 1012742, 1012743, 1012744, 1012745, 1012746.

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012738, 1012739, 1012743, and 1012746 (BOLD:AAA4132, mean *p*-distance 0.73%), with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. sylvaticus* from Germany BOLD:AAA4132, mean *p*-distance 0.51%).

Remarks. Transpalearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Georgia and N Caucasus. In Georgia, it was previously reported only from the Samachablo region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *C. sylvaticus* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Ceratinella brevis* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Kojori; N41.67450°, E44.69962°; 1400 m a.s.l.; xerothermic shrubland near pines, litter; leg. S. Otto; 12 May 2009; KVS 391 • 2♀♀, 1♂; Didgori Vill.; N41.7848°, E44.6757°; 796 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1021038, 1021039, 1021040 • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8025°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, near stream bank, leaf litter; 9 Jul. 2022; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; CaBOL-ID 1027313. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9752°, E44.1044°; 593 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020721. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Martvili Mun., Lebarde; N42.7382°, E42.5006°; 1625 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027144.

Genetics. Two barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020721 and 1027313 (BOLD:AAK0807, *p*-distance 1.82%) with the best match in BOLD Systems as follows: CaBOL-ID 1020721 to *C. brevis* from Norway (BOLD:AAK0807, *p*-distance 1.54%); CaBOL-ID 1027313 to *C. brevis* from Finland (BOLD:AAK0807, *p*-distance 0.92%).

Remarks. A very abundant species widely distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023) and Palearctic (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Diplocephalus latifrons* (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1863)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♂♂; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.3600°, E43.7107°; 2223 m a.s.l.; Abuli forest, leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 28 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-IDs 1012750, 1012751 • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Poka Vill.; N41.3742°, E43.7731°; 2125 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 9 Nov. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012771.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012750 (BOLD:AAD3538) with the nearest neighbor n BOLD Systems f *D. latifrons* from France (BOLD:AAD3538, *p*-distance 1.75%).

Remarks. A very abundant species widely distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023), Turkey, and the European part of the Palaearctic (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Diplostyla concolor* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Ninotsminda Mun., Madatapa Managed Reserve; N41.1968°, E43.7587°; 2128 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 11 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018673 • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.4370°, E43.3078°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018808 • Borjomi Mun., Qvabiskhevi Vill.; N41.7885°, E43.2372°; 986 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032707, 1032708. Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.7698°, E44.7698°; 434 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 28 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020255, 1020316 • 1♀, 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7711°, E44.7687°; 436 m a.s.l.; under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1021007, 1020999.

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1018673, 1018808, 1020255, and 1020316 (BOLD:AAB2008, mean *p*-distance 1.5%), with the nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems are as follows: to CaBOL-ID 1018673 *D. concolor* from Finland (BOLD:AAB2008, *p*-distance 1.46%); CaBOL-ID 101808 to *D. concolor* from France (BOLD:AAB2008, *p*-distance 0.31%); CaBOL-IDs 1020255 and 1020316 identical to *D. concolor* from Canada (BOLD:AAB2008).

Remarks. A very abundant species widely distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023), Palaearctic, and Nearctic (WSC 2023). Previous records of this species from Georgia originate from the Abkhazia and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *D. concolor* from Tbilisi and the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Drapetisca socialis* (Sundevall, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Adigeni Mun., Abastumani; N41.7898°, E42.8529°; 1451 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, on tree trunk; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032067.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this common species is recorded in Azerbaijan, Georgia, and N Caucasus. In Georgia, it was previously reported only from Oni (Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *D. socialis* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Erigone dentipalpis* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; Alazani R., under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010001 • 1♂; N41.1247°, E46.6493°; 105 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1023798 • Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2740°, E45.8876°; 269 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1023786. Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 2300 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 7 – 8 Sep. 2018; KVS 522. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; 1♂; Khobis Mun., Kolkheti NP; N42.33802°, E41.61131°; 301 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 2 Aug. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1030860, 1030861.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1023786 and 1023798 (BOLD:AAB6851, *p*-distance 0.46%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *E. dentipalpis* from Egypt (BOLD:AAB6851, maximum *p*-distance 0.33%).

Remarks. A very abundant species with Holarctic distribution (WSC 2023) and numerous records throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023).

***Erigonoplus globipes* (L. Koch, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.77055°, E44.76689°; 449 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020311 (Fig. 38).

Remarks. European species with records from Turkey and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded in Armenia and Russia (Stavropol Krai) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Erigonoplus* Simon, 1884 in Georgia.

***Frontinellina frutetorum* (C.L. Koch, 1835)**

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 2♀♀; Dusheti Mun., Matura Valley; N42.44441°, E45.07033°; 1500 m a.s.l.; montane grassland; leg. S. Otto; 21 Jul. 2007; KVS 63. Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; meadow at Alazani R., on vegetation; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010007.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010007 (BOLD:AAI5655) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *F. frutetorum* from Slovenia (BOLD:AAI5655).

Remarks. A very abundant species with numerous records throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023) and West Palaearctic (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Gnathonarium dentatum* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Guria • 2♂♂, 8♀♀, 8 juv.; Khobi Mun., E of Paliastomi L.; N42.0846°, E41.7673°; 10 m a.s.l.; leg. B. Chitadze; 29 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035826, 1035827, 1035828, 1035829, 1035830, 1035831, 1035832, 1035833, 1035834, 1035835, 1035836, 1035837, 1035838, 1035839, 1035840, 1035841, 1035842, 1035843.

Figures 38–41. *Erigonoplus globipes*, female (38: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*). *Ipa terrenus* (39: female, epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*; 40: male, left palp, retrolateral view). *Maso gallicus*, male (41: left palp, retrolateral view).

Remarks. An abundant species with Palearctic distribution (WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. In Georgia, *G. dentatum* is distributed only in the eastern part of the country (Otto 2023). This is the first record from the Guria region.

***Gonatium rubens* (Blackwall, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♀♀; Mes-tia Mun., Ushba Peak; N43.0320°, E42.9171°; 3145 m a.s.l.; montane grassland; leg. L. Mumladze; CaBOL-IDs 1012741, 1012768.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012741 (BOLD:AA7687) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *G. rubens* from Norway (BOLD:AA7687, *p*-distance 0.81%).

Remarks. An abundant species with Palearctic distribution (WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Georgia, Azerbaijan, and N Caucasus. In Georgia, *G. rubens* was previously reported from the Abkhazia and Adjara (Otto 2023). This is the first record from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region.

***Ipa keyserlingi* (Ausserer, 1867)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7695°, E44.7670°; 460 m a.s.l.; meadow, moss layer near *Pinus* sp. artificial planting; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020242. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3529°, E43.2518°; 1315 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032728.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020242 (BOLD:ACU8094) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *I. keyserlingi* from Germany (BOLD:ACU8094, *p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. This species has a disjunctive European distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023) with the only record in the Caucasus from Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *I. keyserlingi* from Tbilisi, the Shida Kartli, and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

****Ipa terrenus* (L. Koch, 1879)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9806°, E44.0920°; 586 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rock;

leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020299 (Fig. 39) • 1♀; N41.9847, E44.1414°; 668 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 04 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020826 (Fig. 40) • 2♀♀; Kvernaki ridge; N41.9847, E44.1414°; 668m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 8 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020854, 1020855.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020299 (BOLD:AAU4598) which is the first one of this species submitted to the BOLD Systems.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *I. terrenus* from Georgia.

Lepthyphantes cruentatus Tanasevitch, 1987

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8103°, E44.6954°; 921 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020319.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020319 (BOLD:AEU0783) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *Lepthyphantes* sp. with an unknown place of origin (BOLD:AEU0783, *p*-distance 0.15%). There are no barcodes of this species in BOLD Systems at the moment, as we submit the first one, but given the small genetic distance between our specimen and the unidentified *Lepthyphantes* sp. from Turkey, that presumably belongs to the same species.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus (but see the genetics part) where it is recorded in Georgia and NE Caucasus (Otto 2023).

**Maso gallicus* Simon, 1894

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂; Dighomi Park; N41.7683°, E44.7702°; 430 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023900 (Supplementary File), 1023901 (Fig. 41).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Mediterranean east to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia. Previously it was known from Russia (Ingushetia) and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023).

Maso sundevalli (Westring, 1851)

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.72866°, E42.07702°; 970 m a.s.l.; beech-chestnut forest, litter; leg. S. Otto; 3 Jun. 2009; KVS 472. Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Park; N41.7683°, E44.7702°; 430 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023902.

Remarks. The species has a Holarctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023) with records in the Caucasus from Georgia and N Caucasus (Otto 2023).

**Mecopisthes peusi* Wunderlich, 1972

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 2♀♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8005°, E44.6821°; 892 m a.s.l.; edge of deciduous forest; xero-

thermic slope, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1021026 (Fig. 42), 1021027 (Fig. 43), 1021028.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from Spain east to the Caucasus and south to Israel (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded from Russia (North Ossetia–Alania) (Otto 2023). It is the record of *M. peusi* from Georgia and S Caucasus ecoregion.

Megalephyphantes pseudocollinus Saaristo, 1997

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9645°, E44.0954°; 932 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 23 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018696.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018696 (BOLD:AAU1288) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. pseudocollinus* from Russia with Private status (*p*-distance 0.63%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from Central Europe east to West Siberia and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded from N Caucasus and Georgia (Kakheti region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *M. pseudocollinus* from the Shida Kartli region.

Metopobactrus prominulus (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1873)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7677°, E44.7705°; 532 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, meadow, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 19 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018706. Kakheti • 2♂♂, 4♀♀; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; suburban area, malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 24 Apr. – 1 May 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012869, 1012870, 1012871, 1012872, 1012873, 1012874.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018706 (BOLD:AFI9848) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. prominulus* from Switzerland (BOLD:AAN9621, *p*-distance 1.55%).

Remarks. Species with a Holarctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A common species in the Caucasus recorded from all the countries except Armenia. In Georgia, it was previously known from the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *M. prominulus* from Tbilisi and the Kakheti region.

Microneta viaria (Blackwall, 1841)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 7♂♂, 7♀♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; ravine, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011193, 1011194, 1011195, 1011196, 1011197, 1011198, 1011199, 1020756, 1020757, 1020758, 1020759, 1020760, 1020761, 1020762 • 1♀; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011167 • 2♂♂; Dighomi park; N41.7677°, E44.7705°; 532 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 22 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018714, 1018715.

Genetics. Fourteen barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL IDs 1011167, 1011193, 1011195,

Figures 42–45. *Mecopisthes peusi*, (42: male, left palp, retrolateral view; 43: female, epigyne, prepared, ventral view). *Panamomops sulcifrons*, male (44: left palp, retrolateral view; 45: prosoma, dorsal view).

1011196, 1011198, 1011199, 1018715, 1020756, 1020757, 1020758, 1020759, 1020760, 1020761, and 1020762 (BOLD:AAL5943, mean p -distance 1.71%). The nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems to the specimens are as follows: CaBOL-IDs 1011167, 1011195, and 1011198 *M. varia* from China with Private status (mean p -distance 1.05%); CaBOL-IDs 1011193, 1011196, 1011199, 1018715, 1020756, 1020757, 1020758, 1020759, 1020760, 1020761 and 1020762 *M. varia* from Germany (BOLD:AAL5943, mean p -distance 0.155%).

Remarks. A very abundant species with a Holarctic distribution in the Caucasus recorded from all the countries (WSC 2023; Otto 2023).

Moebelia penicillata (Westring, 1851)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta mun, Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.0722°, E45.3900°; 431 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, meadow, leaf litter; leg. Cabol team; 27 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031237.

Remarks. Palearctic species, with mainly European distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023) and records from the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is reported from Russia (Adygea) and Georgia (Abkhazia and Imereti regions). It is the first record of *M. penicillata* from the Kakheti region.

Nematogmus sanguinolentus (Walckenaer, 1841)

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Khobi Mun., Torsa Vill.; N42.3590°, E41.7831°; 9 m a.s.l.; windbreak, on grass; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 3 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011640 • 1♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. Gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, meadow, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027143.

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed from the Mediterranean east to Japan (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is reported from Armenia, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia, Adjara, and Imereti regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *N. sanguinolentus* from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region.

Neriene clathrata (Sundevall, 1830)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; settlement, malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 24 Jul. – 31 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012865.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012865 (BOLD:ACF4294) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *N. clathrata* from Fin-

land, Norway, Austria, and Germany (BOLD:ACF4294, *p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Samachablo regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *N. clathrata* from the Kakheti region.

****Neriene furtiva* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Poti Mun., Kolkheti NP; N of Pichori R.; N42.14758°, E41.82526°; 0 m a.s.l.; Sphagnum bog, grass; leg. S. Otto; 17 May 2009; KBS 209.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Mediterranean north to Sweden and east to South Siberia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously reported only from Russia (Adygea) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia and South Caucasus.

***Oedothorax apicatus* (Blackwall, 1850)**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Gardabani Mun., NE of Gachiani (E of Tbilisi); N41.60837°, E44.99576°; 400 m a.s.l.; steppe with shrubs; leg. S. Otto; 21 Mar. 2009; KVS 354.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A common species in the Caucasus, reported from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record for the Kvemo Kartli region.

***Oedothorax meridionalis* Tanasevitch, 1987**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 2♂♂, 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 6 Jul. 2010; KBS 182 • 9♂♂, 2♀♀; N41.67795°, E41.84806°; 260 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, Buxus shrub; leg. S. Otto; 8 Jul. 2010; KBS 186. Samtskhe-Javaketi region • 1♂; Borjomi Mun., Nedzvi Managed Reserve; N41.9010°, E43.5157°; 902 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032075.

Remarks. This species is distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023), Iran, and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it was previously reported from the Abkhazia, Adjara, and Kakheti regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *O. meridionalis* from Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

****Oedothorax retusus* (Westring, 1851)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♀♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025688, 1025689. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. Gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027694 • 1♀; Tsalenjikha Mun., Skuri; N42.6880°, E42.1606°; 437 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027696.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded only from Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Palliduphantes khobarum* (Charitonov, 1947)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9693°, E44.0948°; 932 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018740. Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8022°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021024. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Adigeni Mun., Abastumani; N41.7898°, E42.8529°; 1451 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032742.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018740 (BOLD:AAX1847) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. khobarum* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 1.38%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from Greece to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is reported from N Caucasus, Azerbaijan, and Georgia (Samachablo and Guria regions). It is the first record of the species from Tbilisi, the Shida Kartli, and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

****Panamomops sulcifrons* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.7711°, E44.7687°; 436 m a.s.l.; highway, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020720 (Figs 44–45).

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this European species was recorded only from Russia (Adygea) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia and South Caucasus.

***Pelecopsis crassipes* Tanasevitch, 1987**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂, 2♀♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KBS 204. Tbilisi • 9♂♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7820°, E44.7000°; 732 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020742, 1020743, 1020744, 1020745, 1020768, 1020769, 1020770, 1020771, 1020772 • 18♂♂, 13♀♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 799 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011147, 1011148, 1011150, 1011172, 1011173, 1011174, 1011175, 1011176, 1011177, 1011178, 1011179, 1011180, 1011181, 1011149, 1011151, 1011152, 1011153, 1011154, 1011155, 1011156, 1011157, 1011158, 1011159, 1011160, 1011161, 1011162, 1011163, 1011168, 1011169, 1011170, 1011171.

Genetics. Eight virtually identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011149, 1011150, 1011154, 1011160, 1011161, 1011163, 1011168, and 1011178 (BOLD:AFH1054, mean *p*-distance 0.01%). There are no barcodes of this species in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus (WSC 2023). It is the first record of the species from the Kakheti region (Otto 2023).

****Plesiophantes joosti* Heimer, 1981**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂, 1♀; Khelvachauri Mun., Sarpı Vill.; N41.52139°, E41.55194°; 100 m a.s.l.; steep slope; leg. S. Otto; 17 Aug. 2007; KVS 281.

Remarks. Known only from Turkey and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, the species was recorded only from Russia (Krasnodar Krai) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Plesiophantes* Heimer, 1981 from Georgia and South Caucasus. Previous record from the Caucasian State Nature Biosphere Reserve (Tanasevitch 1987) is based on the misidentification of *P. tanasevitchi* Wunderlich, 2011 (Wunderlich 2011).

***Plesiophantes simplex* Tanasevitch, 1987**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 3♂♂, 5♀♀; Kobuleti mun, Mtirala NP; N41.67795°, E41.84806°; 260 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, Buxus shrubs; leg. S. Otto; 8 Jul. 2010; KBS 186 • 1♂, 1♀; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; R. bed; leg. S. Otto; 6 Jul. 2010; KVS 330 • 1♂, 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP, Zeraboseli Vill.; KBS 218. Racha-Lechkhumi and Kve-mo Svaneti region • 5♂♂, 11♀♀; Tkibuli Mun., Nakerala Ridge; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest, branches; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 188.

Remarks. This species is endemic to W Georgia (WSC 2023).

****Poecilonea variegata* (Blackwall, 1841)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.4380°, E43.6462°; 3267 m a.s.l.; leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 12 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012773 (Fig. 46). Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Kazbegi Mun., Stepantsminda station.; N42.655°, E44.649°; 1821 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 7 Jul. 2019.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded in N Caucasus. It is the first record of *Poecilonea* Kulczyński, 1894 from Georgia and South Caucasus (Otto 2023).

****Porrhomma microphthalmum* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2740°, E45.8876°; 269 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023819 (Fig. 47).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023819 (BOLD:AAP2515) identical in the BOLD Systems to the COI genes of *P. microphthalmum* from Russia and Germany with Early-Release and Private statuses.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded only in Russia (Adygea) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from Georgia and the South Caucasus.

Figures 46–50. *Poecilonea variegata*, female (46: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*). *Porrhomma microphthalmum*, female (47: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*). *Porrhomma montanum*, male (48: left palp, retrolateral view). *Sintula retroversus* (49: male, left palp, retrolateral view; 50: female, epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*).

****Porrhomma montanum* Yaginuma & Nishikawa, 1971**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Ninotsminda Mun., Poka Vill.; N41.3742°, E43.7731°; 2125 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 9 Nov. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012761 (Fig. 48).

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species was recorded only in Russia (Karachay-Cherkessia) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from Georgia and the South Caucasus. It is one of the species with a disjunct Caucaso-Far East distribution.

***Scutepelecopsis krausi* (Wunderlich, 1980)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♀♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. Gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027158, 1030855.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species is recorded from Armenia and Georgia (Samtskhe-Javakheti region). It is the first record of *S. krausi* from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region. In Europe, the species is known from Italy and the Balkan Peninsula (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Scutepelecopsis wunderlichi* Marusik & Gnelitsa, 2009**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8016°, E44.6789°; 913 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Jan. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1011126.

Remarks. This species has a Caucaso-Iranian distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously reported from N Caucasus and Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *S. wunderlichi* from Tbilisi.

****Sintula retroversus* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.76774°, E44.77048°; 532 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 22 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018704 (Fig. 49), 1018705 (Fig. 50) • 1♂, 1♀; Mukhatgverdi; N41.80886°, E44.70656°; 847 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020317, 1020287. Shida Kartli • 2♂♂, 2♀♀; Gori; N41.96933°, E44.09483°; 932 m a.s.l.; forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018710, 1018711, 1018712 and 1018713 • 1♂; N41.9752°, E44.1044°; 593 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011205.

Genetics. Six identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1018704, 1018705, 1018710, 1018712, 1020287, and 1020317 (BOLD:AFH2460) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *S. retroversus* from Bulgaria with Private status (*p*-distance 1.71%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from Spain east to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded from Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Russia (North Ossetia-Alania). It is the first record of *S. retroversus* from Georgia.

***Stemonyphantes agnatus* Tanasevitch, 1990**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 3♀♀; Borjomi Mun., Bakuriani; N41.74874°, E43.52776°; 2100 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 17 Sep. 2011; KVS 314, KBS 160 • 1♀; Qvabiskhevi Vill.; N41.7885°, E43.2372°; 986 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032760. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♀♀; Martvili Mun., Taleri Vill., Tekhuri R. valley; N42.53889°, E42.34972°; 400 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 10 Oct. 2011; KVS 305 • 1♂; Tbilisi, Kojori; N41.6439°, E44.6981°; 1266 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 28 Mar. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009776. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Khashuri Mun., Kvishkheti Vill.; N41.9613°, E43.5116°; 723 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R., roadside, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018810

Genetics. A single barcode obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018810 (BOLD:AFH1035) is the first one of this species to be submitted to the BOLD Systems.

Remarks. A very abundant Ponto-Caucasian species (Nentwig et al. 2023), in the Caucasus recorded in Georgia, Azerbaijan, and NE Caucasus (Otto 2023).

****Stemonyphantes lineatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Adigeni Mun., 2 km SW of Ijareti Vill.; N41.64895°, E42.70120°; 1503 m a.s.l.; forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 9 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018803 (Fig. 51). Shida Kartli • 1♂, 2♀♀; Gori; N41.7695°, E44.7737°; 588 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. bank, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1031257, 1031258, 1031259.

Remarks. Transpalaeartic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously recorded in Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *S. lineatus* from Georgia.

***Styloctetor romanus* (O. P.-Cambridge, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9872°, E44.1499°; 716 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011201 • 1♀, 1♂; N41.9872°, E44.1499°, 713 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; 21 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011201, 1021000 • 1♀; Gori; N41.9693°, E44.0948°; 932 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018733. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2740°, E45.8876°; 269 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023793.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023793 (BOLD:AAP2516), identical in BOLD Systems to *S. romanus* from Germany (BOLD:AAP2516).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from North Africa east to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded from Armenia, Azerbaijan, Russia (Stavropol Krai), and Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from the Shida Kartli and Kakheti regions.

Figures 51–54. *Stemonyphantes lineatus*, male (51: left palp, retrolateral view). *Tiso vagans*, female (52: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*). *Theonina cornix*, female (53: endogyne, dorsal view, expanded and rotated). *Trichopterna cito*, female (54: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*).

****Tallusia experta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Bughdasheni Managed Reserve; N41.19855°, E43.68844°; 2042 m a.s.l.; meadow, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020329 (Supplementary File).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020329 (BOLD:AA7646) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. experta* from Finland (BOLD:AA7646, *p*-distance 0.8%).

Remarks. Transpalearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). It is the first record of *Tallusia* Lehtinen & Saaristo, 1972 from Georgia. Previously it was known within the Caucasus from Azerbaijan and Russia (North Osetia) (Otto 2023).

***Tapinopa longidens* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 2♂♂; Gori; N41.9794°, E44.0908°; 586 m a.s.l.; floodplain, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Sep. 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1035484, 1035485.

Remarks. This species has a Palearctic distribution (except for Iran, Central Asia, and North Africa) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Armenia and Georgia (Adjara). It is the first record of *T. longidens* from the Shida Kartli region.

***Tenuiphantes contortus* (Tanasevitch, 1986)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Ninotsminda; N41.2949°, E43.5334°; 1897 m a.s.l.; leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 5 Jul. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012740.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus, recorded throughout the whole region. In Georgia, it was previously reported from the Kakheti and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. contortus* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Tenuiphantes mendei* (Kulczyński, 1887)**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP, Chakvistavi R., near waterfall; N41.67495°, E41.87580°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2010; KBS 184. Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂; Telovani vill.; N41.8103°, E44.6954°; 921 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020275, 1020288.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020275 and 1020288 (BOLD:AAQ0207, *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. mendei* from Switzerland (BOLD:AA7646, mean *p*-distance 0.235%).

Remarks. A very abundant species recorded throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023) and Palearctic (except for Turkey, East Asia, North Africa, and Iran).

***Tenuiphantes tenuis* (Blackwall, 1852)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Vere Valley; N41.71152°, E44.69418°; 633 m a.s.l.; xerothermic Paliurus shrubs, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 27 Mar. 2009; KBS 191. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9693°, E44.0948°; 932 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018698. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3762°, E43.2763°; 1237 m a.s.l.; meadow, un-

der rock; leg. A. Seropian; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018699 • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Gandzani Vill.; N41.3554°, E43.6984°; 2313 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 19 Aug. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012747 • 1♀; Poka Vill.; N41.3742°, E43.7731°; 2125 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 9 Nov. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012748.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1018698 and 1018699 (BOLD:AAG9172, *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. tenuis* from Canada (BOLD:AAG9172, mean *p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. An abundant holarctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023) recorded throughout the whole Caucasus. In Georgia, it was previously reported from Tbilisi, the Kakheti, Samtskhe-Javakheti, and Adjara (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. tenuis* from the Shida Kartli region.

*****Theonina cf. cornix* (Simon, 1881)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; meadow, ravine, stream bank, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021008 (Fig. 52) • 1♀; N41.7818°, E44.7086°; 629 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 19 Nov. 2022.

Remarks. This species has a disjunct Mediterranean-European distribution. It was not recorded in the Caucasus previously (Nentwig et al. 2023). *Theonina kratovchili* Miller & Weiss, 1979 is the only congener previously recorded in the Caucasus (Georgia and the N Caucasus) (Otto 2023). Females of the genus are hard to distinguish (scapus longer than wide in *T. cornix*, while in *T. kratovchili* it's wide and quadrangular). For reliable identification of this species, a male is required.

****Tiso vagans* (Blackwall, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2363°, E45.2857°; 1298 m a.s.l.; broad-leaved forest, under dead wood bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili.; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025537 (Fig. 53) • 1♀; Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili.; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025822.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1025822 (BOLD:AAY8144), identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. vagans* from Belarus BOLD:AAY8144).

Remarks. This species has a primarily Western European distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023) with a single record in the Caucasus from Alania, North Ossetia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Tiso* Simon, 1884 from Georgia.

****Trichopterna cito* (O.Pickard-Cambridge, 1873)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N44.7798°, E41.7195°; 440 m a.s.l.; malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 16 – 31 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012834 (Fig. 54).

Remarks. This species has a primarily Western European distribution, with records from Kazakhstan and the Cauca-

sus (except for Armenia and Georgia) (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Trichopterna* Kulczyński, 1894 from Georgia.

***Troglohyphantes adjaricus* Tanasevitch, 1987**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 1200 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 21 – 22 Sep. 2018; KVS 516.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus, recorded (and described) from Georgia (Adjara) and Russia (Karachay-Cherkessia) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023).

****Troglohyphantes birsteini* Charitonov, 1947**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Tsalenjikha Mun., Skuri; N42.6880°, E42.1606°; 437 m a.s.l.; rock pile; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027695.

Remarks. The troglobiont species endemic to the Caucasus, previously recorded only from Russia (Krasnodar Krai) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

****Typhochrestus inflatus* Thaler, 1980**

GEORGIA • 1♀; Tbilisi, Vere Valley; N41.70865°, E44.69501°; 700 m a.s.l.; moist river bed, between rocks; leg. S. Otto; 27 Mar. 2009; KVS 358.

Remarks. Species with very disjunctive Palaearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it was recorded only from Azerbaijan. It is the first record of *Typhochrestus* Simon, 1884 in Georgia.

***Walckenaeria alticeps* (Denis, 1952)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂, 3♀♀; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.3600°, E43.7107°; 2223 m a.s.l.; Abuli forest, leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 28 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-IDs 1012749, 1012742, 1012775, 1012776.

Genetics. Four nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012742, 1012749, 1012775, and 1012776 (BOLD:AFH0867, maximum *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems *W. alticeps* from Germany (BOLD:AFH0867, mean *p*-distance 1.6%) and *W. antica* (Wider, 1834) from Germany (BOLD:AFH0867, mean *p*-distance 1.6%).

Remarks. The identification via COI gene was not straightforward, as it failed to distinguish *W. alticeps* from *W. antica*, although it's worth noting, that the determination of these similar and strongly related species has caused some confusion in the past: males of both species are almost identical in the structure of their palps (only the diameter of embolus may be slightly different), but epigyne and endogyne are quite distinct as their ecological claims are, too: *alticeps* is characterized as hygrobiont, and *antica* as photophilous-xerophilous, although both may exist in the same locality (Wunderlich 2008). In the Caucasus, this species was previously recorded from N Caucasus and Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *W. alticeps* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

****Walckenaeria bifasciculata* Tanasevitch, 1987**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 3♀♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 388. – Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7820°, E44.7000°; 732 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; 10 Dec. 2021; leg. Bulbulashvili N.; CaBOL-IDs 1020782 (Figs 55–56), 1020783 (Figs 57–60) • 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.7681°, E44.7717°; 413 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032347.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus, previously recorded in Armenia and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

*****Walckenaeria cf. corniculans* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1875)**

GEORGIA • 1♀; Tbilisi, Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; 628 m a.s.l.; meadow, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; 15 Dec. 2021, leg. Bulbulashvili N.; CaBOL-ID 1020801 (Fig. 61).

Remarks. The nearest known distribution of this species is Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023), as we report it from the Caucasus for the first time. Species verification requires a male specimen since the females have very simple epigynes.

****Walckenaeria monoceros* (Wider, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.96933°, E44.09483°; 932 m a.s.l.; forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018734 • 1♂; N41.9820°, E44.0879°; 586 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020779 (Figs 62–63) • 2♂♂; Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9956°, E44.1512°; 783 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020303, 1020304.

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1018734, 1020303, 1020304, and 1020779 (BOLD:ABY2804, mean *p*-distance 1.58%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *W. monoceros* from Germany (BOLD:ABY2804, mean *p*-distance 1.53%).

Figures 55–60. *Walckenaeria bifasciculata*, female (55: epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 56: endogyne, dorsal view), male (57: left palp, retrolateral view; 58: tibial apophysis, dorsal view; 59: prosoma, lateral view; 60: same, dorsal view).

Figures 61–63. *Walckenaeria corniculans*, female (**61**: endogyne, dorsal view). *Walckenaeria monoceros*, male (**62**: left palp, retrolateral view; **63**: tibial apophysis, dorsal view).

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed from Spain east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was recorded in Azerbaijan and the N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from Georgia.

Family Liocranidae Simon, 1897

***Agroeca brunnea* Blackwall, 1833

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9794°, E44.0908°; Mtkvari R. floodplain, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035471 (Figs 64–65).

Remarks. This species has a wide Palearctic distribution (except for the Caucasus, North Africa, Central Asia, and Iran) (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *A. brunnea* from the Caucasus. The nearest record to Georgia is from Turkey (Gündüz and Allahverdi 2018).

Agroeca cuprea Menge, 1873

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, near Gorijvari; N41.97702°, E44.08040°; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Sep. 2020; KVS 562; CaBOL-ID 1004214.

Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.76946°, E44.77374°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 15 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012555 • 1♂; N41.76947°, E44.77374°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 14 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010391 • 1♀; N41.76978°, E44.76984°; 943421 m a.s.l.; meadow, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 28 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020325 • 1♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 799 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011123. Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, in leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025549.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012555 and 1020325 (BOLD:ABA7471) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. cuprea* from Norway (BOLD:ABA7471, mean *p*-distance 0.78%).

Remarks. Species with Palearctic distribution (except for Turkey and East Asia) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. cuprea* from Tbilisi, the Shida Kartli, and Kakheti regions.

Figures 64–65. *Agroeca brunnea*, male (64: left palp, ventral view; 65: same, retrolateral view).

**Agroeca lusatica* (L. Koch, 1875)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Tsalka Mun., S of Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; subalpine *Artemisia* grassland, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 417 • 1♀; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; subalpine *Artemisia* grassland, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 30 May 2009; KVS 417 • 1♀; Akhalkalaki Mun., Bozali Vill.; N41.2706°, E43.3372°; 1888 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze, 8 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023865 (Supplementary File).

Remarks. Species with Palaearctic distribution (except for Turkey and East Asia) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. lusatica* in the South Caucasus.

**Mesiotelus caucasicus* Zamani & Marusik, 2021

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3529°, E43.2518°; 1315 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032038 (Fig. 66).

Remarks. This species is recorded in Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Mesiotelus* Simon, 1897 from Georgia.

Family Lycosidae Sundevall, 1833

Alopecosa albofasciata (Brullé, 1832)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂ (subadult); Tbilisi; N41.7698°, E44.7661°; 452 m a.s.l.; artificial pine forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 4 Jan. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009817.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1009817 (BOLD:AFH4131) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. albofasciata* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 2.1%).

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it was recorded from Azerbaijan, NE Caucasus, and the eastern part of Georgia (Otto 2023).

**Alopecosa cronebergi* (Thorell, 1875)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli region • 1♂; Gori; N41.971983°, E44.097053°; 720 m a.s.l.; montane, xerothermic slope; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Oct. 2019; CaBOL-ID 1004198 (Fig. 67) • 1♀; N41.97523°, E44.09826°; 649 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018742 • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.98477°, E44.13893°; 696 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 23 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018743 • 1♂; N41.9991°, E44.1431°; 788 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012907.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004198 and 1018743 (BOLD:AFG9832) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. solitaria* from an unknown place of origin (BOLD:AAP3201; mean *p*-distance 1.43%). The identification via COI gene was not straightforward. There are no barcodes of *A. cronebergi* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. This species is distributed from Slovakia east to Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously recorded in Azerbaijan

Figures 66–67. *Mesiotelus caucasicus*, female (66: endogyne, dorsal view). *Alopecosa cronebergi*, male (67: left palp, retrolateral view).

and NE Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this large lycosid from Georgia.

Alopecosa cuneata (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Artsivis Kheoba (Eagle Gorge); N41.4900°, E46.0975°; 754 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023758 • 2♂♂; Akhmeta Mun., Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025752, 1025753.

Genetics. Tree nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1023758, 1025752, and 1025753 (BOLD:AAE5793, mean *p*-distance 0.41%) that had a good match with *A. cuneata* from Germany (BOLD:AAE5793, mean *p*-distance 0.62%) in BOLD Systems.

Remarks. Abundant species with a Palearctic distribution (except for Iran and parts of West and Central Asia) (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is widely distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (except for Armenia and NW Caucasus) (Otto 2023).

Alopecosa inquilina (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Adigeni Mun., SW of Zazma vill.; N41.64793°, E42.59671°; 1595 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest edge; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 9 Oct.

2021; CaBOL-ID 1018688 • 1♂; Akhalkalaki Mun., Tetrobi Managed Reserve; N41.5631°, E43.3533°; 1924 m a.s.l.; coniferous forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032048 • 1♂, 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Damala Vill.; N41.5726°, E43.3140°; 1721 m a.s.l.; Quercus sp. forest edge; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and M. Todua; 12 Oct. 2022.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018688 (BOLD:ACT1390), nearly identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. inquilina* from Finland (BOLD:ACT1390), mean *p*-distance 0.62%.

Remarks. Palearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded only in Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. inquilina* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

Alopecosa pulverulenta (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Adjara • 2♂♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 2400 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 24. – 25 Aug. 2018; KVS 527. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 5♂♂, 2♀♀; Akhmeta Mun., Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025664, 1025665, 1025775, 1025776, 1025777, 1025778, 1025779.

Genetics. Five nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1025775, 1025776,

1025777, 1025778, and 1025779 (BOLD:AAE5793, maximum *p*-distance 0.61%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. purlverulenta* from Finland (BOLD:AAE5793, mean *p*-distance 0.31%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023) with numerous records from the Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from the Adjara.

Alopecosa sulzeri (Pavesi, 1873)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Kojori; N41.6763°, E44.7011°; 1385 m a.s.l.; pine forest; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009764.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1009764 (BOLD:ABU6167), nearly identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. sulzeri* from Slovenia (BOLD:ABU6167, mean *p*-distance 0.77%).

Remarks. This species is distributed from Spain east to South Siberia and Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is not recorded only in Armenia (Otto 2023).

Alopecosa taeniopus (Kulczynski, 1895)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.7832°, E44.6826°; 815 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016822 • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7828°, E44.7004°, 715 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rock; 3 Mar. 2020; leg. A. Seropian; KBS 369 • 1♂; N41.7828°, E44.7004°, 715 m a.s.l.; meadow, on mosses; leg. A. Seropian; 14 Mar. 2020, ex coll. KBS 370. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Akhaltsikhe Mun., Uraeli Gorge; N41.6145°, E43.0371°; 986 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018747 • 3♂♂, 1♀; Aspindza Mun., above Vardzia; N41.38793°, E43.27602°; 1800 m a.s.l.; subalpine, S-exposed meadow, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 6 Apr. 2009; KBS 198, KVS 374. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9822°, E44.0871°; 588 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021054. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba vill.; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; pseudosteppe, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 11 Aug. 2007; KVS 265.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016822 and 1018747 (BOLD:AFH1984, *p*-distance 0.91%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems as follows: for CaBOL-ID 1016822 *A. taeniopus* from Bulgaria with a Private status (*p*-distance 1.82%); for CaBOL-ID 1018787 *A. taeniopus* from Russia (BOLD:AAH8591; mean *p*-distance 1.54%).

Remarks. Distributed from Greece to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the description of the species Mcheidze (1997) mentions the dark yellow sternum, which was pitch black in all of our freshly preserved specimens. In the Caucasus, this species is not recorded only in Armenia (Otto 2023).

Arctosa personata (L. Koch, 1872)

GEORGIA – Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti • 1♀; Tsageri Mun., Zubi Vill.; N42.56777°, E42.66887°; 450 m

a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 23 Sep. 2011; KVS 309. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9827°, E44.0872°, 700 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R., under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 May 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004199 • 1♂; N41.9826°, E44.0872°, 588 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R., under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 25 Oct. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004251 • 1♀; N41.97760°, E44.10620°; 590 m a.s.l.; under st; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012357. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.11183°, E46.64949°; 93 m a.s.l.; Alazani R. bank; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010073.

Remarks. This species has a disjunctive Western Mediterranean-Caucasian distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Azerbaijan, NE Caucasus, and Georgia (Samachablo region). It is the first record of *A. personata* from the Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti, Shida Kartli, and Kakheti regions. It is possible, that poorly depicted and described *A. lagodechiansis* Mcheidze, 1997 is a junior synonym of *A. personata*.

Arctosa tbilisiensis Mcheidze, 1946

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Khevidzmari R.; N41.8081°, E44.8496°; 534 m a.s.l.; under log, leg. A. Seropian; 15 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010057. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro; N41.4642°, E46.0953°; 808 m a.s.l.; pitfall; leg. A. Seropian; 16. – 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010072. Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 430 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 14. – 15 Jun. 2018; KVS 530. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♂♂; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027706.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010057 and 1010072 (BOLD:ACK6582; *p*-distance 0.37%), identical with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *A. tbilisiensis* from an unknown place of origin (BOLD:ACK6582).

Remarks. This species is distributed from Greece to Azerbaijan and south to Iran. A very abundant species occurs throughout almost the whole Caucasus (except for Armenia). It is the first record of this species from the Adjara and Kakheti regions (Otto 2023).

Geolycosa charitonovi (Mcheidze, 1997)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., Tbatana; N42.2680°, E45.2588°; 1931 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 6 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1025692.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus. The record from India presumably belongs to the undescribed species (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Lycosa singoriensis (Laxmann, 1770)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 2♂♂; Gardabani Mun., Nagebi Vill.; N41.502262°, E45.096478°; 330 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. S. Otto; 2 Aug. 2013; KVS 174. Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareji, Kapatadze L.; N41.5717°, E45.3200°; 823 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 6 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010298.

Remarks. Distributed from Central Europe to East Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). This species is distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia). In Georgia, it was previously recorded from Tbilisi, the Adjara, and Kakheti regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *L. singoriensis* from the Kvemo Kartli region.

****Pardosa atomaria* (C.L. Koch, 1847)**

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1 ♀; Dusheti Mun., Matura Valley; N42.46317°, E45.09656°; 1800 m a.s.l.; R.bed, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 22 Jul. 2007; KVS 71.

Remarks. This species has a disjunctive Caspico-Ponto-Mediterranean distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded only from Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. atomaria* from Georgia.

***Pardosa azerifalcata* Marusik, Guseinov & Koponen, 2003**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀; Kvareli Mun., Sabue Vill.; N42.0566°, E45.1232°; 634 m a.s.l.; Ilto R. bank, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025684, 1025789, 1025790, 1025791, 1025792.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1025791, and 1025792 (BOLD:AFH1308, *p*-distance 0.15%). There are no barcodes of *P. azerifalcata* available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. This species has a Caspico-Iranian distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Tbilisi). It is the first record of *P. azerifalcata* from the Kakheti region.

***Pardosa buchari* Ovtsharenko, 1979**

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀; Dusheti Mun., Matura Valley; N42.46686°, E45.09244°; 2000 m a.s.l.; montane meadow; leg. S. Otto; 22 Jul. 2007; KVS 69, KVS 70 • 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀; N42.48480°, E45.10867°; 2800 m a.s.l.; alpine grassland; leg. S. Otto; 23 Jul. 2007; KBS 34.

Remarks. The general distribution of this species is Caspico-Iranian with a record in Europe from Ukraine (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is generally distributed along the Greater Caucasus, with records from subalpine and alpine zones (Otto 2023).

***Pardosa caucasica* Ovtsharenko, 1979**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1 ♀; Borjomi Mun., Didi Mitarbi Vill.; N41.7465°, E43.58057°; 1700 m a.s.l.; montane forest; leg. S. Otto; 22 Aug. 2007; KBS 115. Tbilisi • 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; Kojori; N41.67450°, E44.69962°; 1400 m a.s.l.; xerothermic shrubland, litter; leg. S. Otto; 12 May 2009; KBS 205.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus. In Georgia, it is recorded from the Samachablo and Abkhazia regions. It is the first record of *P. caucasica* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Pardosa consimilis* Nosek, 1905**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1 ♀; Telavi Mun., Gombori Pass; N41.86319°, E45.27944°; 1600 m a.s.l.; shrubland, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 23 Aug. 2007; KVS 266.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species was known from a single locality in Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). This species was described from Turkey and is known in the Balkans, Georgia, and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Pardosa incerta* Nosek, 1905**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1 ♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 2400 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 23. – 25 Aug. 2018; KVS 510 • 1 ♀; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 2300 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 5. – 7 Sep. 2018; KVS 511.

Remarks. A very abundant species in the Caucasus distributed along the Greater Caucasus. In Georgia, this species is recorded from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Abkhazia regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Adjara. Outside the Caucasus, this species is known in Bulgaria, Turkey, and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Pardosa italica* Tongiorgi, 1966**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1 ♂; Sagarejo Mun., Kapatadze L., N of Udabno Vill.; N41.57599°, E45.31475°; 800 m a.s.l.; steppe, saline shore, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KBS 203. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; Tsalka Mun., S of Aiazmi Vill.; N41.54993°, E43.88660°; 1900 m a.s.l.; Artemisia grassland, field layer, leg. S. Otto; KBS 216, KVS 416 • 1 ♀; Akhalkalaki Mun., Bozali vill.; N41.2706°, E43.3372°; 1888 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 8 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023876. Tbilisi • 2 ♀♀; Dighomi meadows; N41.7965°, E44.7871°; 418 m a.s.l.; steppe, temporary pools; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 1 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1026426, 1026429.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023876 (BOLD:AAI2651) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. italica* from Turkey (*p*-distance 0.15%) with an Early-release status.

Remarks. Species with a disjunct distribution from Portugal east to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. italica* from the Kakheti and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

****Pardosa luctinosa* Simon, 1876**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Sagarejo Mun., Kapatadze L., N of Udabno Vill.; N41.57599°, E45.31475°; 800 m a.s.l.; steppe, saline shore, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 382.

Remarks. Species with disjunct Palaearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Pardosa morosa* (L. Koch, 1870)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂; Vere Valley; N41.70865°, E44.69501°; 700 m a.s.l.; creek, moist bed, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 27 Mar. 2009; KVS 356 • 1♀; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 13 May 2009; KVS 394.

Remarks. This species is distributed from Portugal to Central Asia and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from the southern part (Georgia, Azerbaijan). The studied material originates from a previously known single locality in the country (Otto 2023).

***Pardosa nebulosa* (Thorell, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♂♂, 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijinskure; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; Alazani R. bank; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1010077, 1010373, 1010005 • 4♀♀, 1♂; Sighnaghi Mun., Erisimedi Vill.; N41.5944, E46.3319; 193 m a.s.l.; Alazani R. bank; leg. L. Ninua and G. Ian-koshvili; 11 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020903, 1035730, 1035731, 1035732, 1035733.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010077 (BOLD) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. nebulosa* from Bulgaria with Private status (*p*-distance 0.35%).

Remarks. Distributed from Italy to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A very abundant species, distributed almost throughout the whole Caucasus (except for Armenia). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Abkhazia, Guria, Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti, Samtskhe-Javakheti, Shida Kartli, Kvemo Kartli, and Adjara (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. nebulosa* from the Kakheti region.

***Pardosa pontica* (Thorell, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀, 1♂; Tsalenjikha Mun., Skuri; N42.6880°, E42.1606°; 437 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027698, 1027699.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1027698, 1027699 (BOLD:AAI2650) identical to the COI of *P. pontica* of unknown origin in BOLD Systems (BOLD:AAI2650) mined from GenBank (MG677955).

Remarks. *Pardosa pontica* is distributed from Bulgaria to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). This species is very abundant in the Caucasus. In Georgia, it is recorded from the Kvemo Kartli, Samtskhe-Javakheti, Kakheti regions, and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region.

*****Pardosa saltans* Töpfer-Hofmann, 2000**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro; N41.4867°, E46.1350°; 716 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023342.

Remarks. *Pardosa saltans* is distributed in Europe and Turkey (the nearest record) (Nentwig et al. 2023). The palp structure of the examined specimen (see Supplementary File) corresponded well with the drawings from Nentwig et al. (2023). It is the first record of this species from the Caucasus.

***Pardosa sphagnicola* (Dahl, 1908)**

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 2♀♀; Dusheti Mun., Matura valley; N42.44441°, E45.07033°; 1500 m a.s.l.; montane grassland; leg. S. Otto; 21 Jul. 2007; KVS 65 • 1♂; N42.46686°, E45.09244°; 2000 m a.s.l.; montane meadow; leg. S. Otto; 22 Jul. 2007; KVS 66.

Remarks. This species has a European distribution, with only two records in the Caucasus (Georgia and Chechnya). It is the first record of *P. sphagnicola* from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti region (Otto 2023).

***Pardosa tatarica* (Thorell, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 4♂♂, 1♀; Lagodekhi Mun., Lagodekhi NP; N41.85977°, E46.30848°; 750 m a.s.l.; beech-hornbeam forest, river bed, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 30 Mar. 2009; KVS 364.

Remarks. *Pardosa tatarica* is distributed from Portugal to Azerbaijan and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded only from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the second record in the country and the first from the Kakheti region.

***Pirata piraticus* (Clerck, 1757)**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Ispani II wetland; N41.86339°, E41.78367°; 6 m a.s.l.; Sphagnum bog, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 19 May 2009; KVS 403.

Remarks. Species with Holarctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. piraticus* from the Adjara.

***Piratula hurkai* (Buchar, 1966)**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 8♀♀; Keda Mun., Zeda Makhuntseti Vill.; N41.57065°, E41.85980°; 100 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, river bed, rock scree; leg. S. Otto; 18 Aug. 2007; KVS 183 • 8♀♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 6 Jul. 2010; KBS 183 • 3♂♂, 2♀♀; N41.67495°, E41.87580°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2010; KVS 335, KBS 184 • 1♂, 3♀♀, 1♂(subadult); Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP, Didvake Vill.; N41.73398°, E42.02444°; 440 m a.s.l.; alder forest, river bed, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 2 Jun. 2009; KBS 219. Kakheti • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; Batsara R. bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025734. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Kareli Mun., Kintsvisi Vill.; N41.9611°, E43.8370°; 1043 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, stream bank;

leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 17 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026358. Tbilisi • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8025°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, stream bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 9 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027302.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1027302 and 1026358 (BOLD:ABA3413), identical to the COI gene of *P. burkai* mined from GenBank from an unknown place of origin (BOLD:ABA3413) in BOLD Systems.

Remarks. This species is known from the Caucasus (Georgia and N Caucasus) and Ukraine (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Abkhazia and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. burkai* from the Adjara, Kakheti, Shida Kartli regions, and Tbilisi.

Piratula latitans (Blackwall, 1841)

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Tianeti Mun., Orkhevi vill.; N41.9743°, E45.0252°; 1009 m a.s.l.; at Iori R. bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025819. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Kareli Mun., Kintsvisi Vill.; N41.9611°, E43.8370°; 1043 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, at the stream bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 17 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026357.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1025819 and 1026357 (BOLD:AAL4142, *p*-distance 0.46%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. latitans* from Germany and France (BOLD:AAL4142, mean *p*-distance 0.23%).

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Iberian Peninsula, west to Azerbaijan, and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in all countries except for Armenia. In Georgia, it is recorded from the Abkhazeti region (Otto 2023). It is the first of *P. latitans* from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Shida Kartli regions.

Trochosa cachetiensis Mcheidze, 1997

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Telovani; N41.8025°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, stream bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 9 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027310.

Genetics. There are no barcodes of *T. cachetiensis* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one, obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1027310 (BOLD:AAM9675) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. terricola* mined from GenBank with unknown place of origin (BOLD:AAM9675, *p*-distance 0.31%). Given such a small genetic distance between our specimen and “*T. terricola*” from unknown location and the fact, that other closest *T. terricola* show a distance of a minimum 3.79%, it can be assumed that the barcode of “*T. terricola*” mined from GenBank should be assigned to *T. cachetiensis*.

Remarks. This species is endemic to the Caucasus (Georgia, N Caucasus) (Otto 2023).

Trochosa hispanica Simon, 1870

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Dusheti Mun., Matura valley; N42.44441°, E45.07033°; 1500 m a.s.l.;

montane grassland; leg. S. Otto; 21 Jul. 2007; KVS 57. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Borjomi Mun., Borjomi NP; N41.89500°, E43.33400°; 1500 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 17 Sep. 2011; KBS 156.

Remarks. The range of this species stretches from the Iberian Peninsula to Tajikistan, north to the Dniπροetrovsk Area in Ukraine, and south to Algeria and Morocco (Marusik and Nadolny 2020). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan, Dagestan, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Samachablo regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. hispanica* from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

**Wadicosa fidelis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♂♂; Dedoplistksaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.28560°, E45.89528°; 288 m a.s.l.; semidesert, puddles; leg. A. Seropian; 19 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1010004 (Fig. 68), 1010079 • 1♀ (Fig. 69), 1♂ (subadult); N41.3253°, E45.9286°; 493 a.s.l.; semidesert, near the dried creek; leg. S. Japarashvili; 18 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1033256, 1033257 • 1♂; Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure, Alazani R.; N41.1118°, E46.6495°; 93 m a.s.l.; river bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023345.

Genetics. Three barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010004 (BOLD:AFH3302), 1010079, and 1023345 (BOLD:AEB1907) (mean *p*-distance 2.1%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *W. fidelis* from Pakistan (BOLD:AEB1907, mean *p*-distance 1%).

Remarks. This species is known from South China, the Mediterranean, the Caucasus (Azerbaijan), West, Central, South, Southeast and East Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Wadicosa* Zyuzin, 1985 from Georgia.

Family Mimetidae Simon, 1881

**Ero koreana* Paik, 1967

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., near Udabno Vill.; N41.51583°, E45.39669°; 857 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 8 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010315. Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi meadows; N41.7965°, E44.7871°; 418 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 1 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026417 (Figs 70–71).

Remarks. This species has a disjunct Palaearctic distribution (WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *E. koreana* from Georgia and the second in the region.

Mimetus laevigatus (Keyserling, 1863)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1249°, E46.6486°; 107 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023329.

Remarks. This species distribution ranges from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (WSC 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded in the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Kakheti region.

Figures 68–69. *Wadicosa fidelis* (68: male, left palp, ventral view; 69: female, epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*).

Figures 70–71. *Ero koreana*, male (70: left palp, retrolateral view; 71: same, prolateral view).

Family Miturgidae Simon, 1886

Zora nemoralis (Blackwall, 1861)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, near Gorijvari; N41.97702°, E44.08040°; 600 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Sep. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004213. Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., between Tianeti and Akhmeta; N42.064°, E45.064°; 1000 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 8 Jul. 2019.

Remarks. This species has a Palearctic distribution (except for Turkey and N Africa) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In

Georgia, this species is recorded from the Samachablo region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Z. nemoralis* from the Shida Kartli and Kakheti regions.

Family Nemesiidae Simon, 1892

Raveniola adjarica Zonstein, Kunt & Yağmur, 2018

GEORGIA – Adjara • 2♂♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7608°, E41.9784°; 430 m a.s.l.; forest, pitfall trap; leg. G. Chaladze; 5 – 8 Sep. 2018; KVS 506.

Remarks. This species is endemic to Georgia (WSC 2023). Previously it was misidentified as *R. pontica* (Zonstein, Kunt & Yağmur, 2018) (Zonstein et al. 2018).

Family Nesticidae Simon, 1894

Aituaria borutzkyi (Reimoser, 1930)

GEORGIA – Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti • 2♂♂, 1♀; Ambrolauri Mun., Shaori L.; N42.42243°, E43.11075°; 1100 m a.s.l.; cave; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 178 • 1♂, 4♀♀; Tsageri Mun., NW of Tvishi; N42.52333°, E42.73389°; 300 m a.s.l.; old mining gallery; leg. F. Walther; 8 Oct. 2011; KVS 301. – Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67495°, E41.87580°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2010; KBS 184 • 1♂; N41.67795°, E41.84806°; 260 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, on Buxus shrub; leg. S. Otto; 8 Jul. 2010; KBS 186. – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♂♂, 2♀♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. Gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1027156, 1027157, 1027662, 1030850.

Remarks. This troglodyte species is recorded from Georgia, Turkey, and Ukraine (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Family Oecobiidae Blackwall, 1862

**Oecobius maculatus* Simon, 1870

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden, rock pile; leg. S. Otto; 11 Aug. 2007; KVS 263. Tbilisi • 2♀♀; Vere Valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 27 Apr. 2009; KBS 200.

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Mediterranean to Azerbaijan, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, *O. maculatus* is recorded in Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

**Oecobius nadiae* (Spassky, 1936)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7124°, E44.7484°; 495 m a.s.l.; building wall; leg. G. Iankoshvili; 24 Jul. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035869 (see supplementary file) • 2♀♀, 1♂; N41.7124°, E44.7484°; 495 m a.s.l.; building wall; leg. A. Seropian; 2 Aug. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035871 (see supplementary file), 1035875, 1035876.

Remarks. The known distribution of this species ranges from Armenia to China. In the Caucasus, *O. nadiae* is recorded in Armenia and Azerbaijan (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

Family Oonopidae Simon, 1890

**Silhouettella osmaniye* Wunderlich, 2011

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro, Vashlovani NP, Pantishara Gorge; N41.2400°, E46.3847°; 459 m a.s.l.;

semidesert, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 18 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020791 • 1♂; Chachuna Managed Reserve, Qila Kupra; N41.3338°, E45.7692°; 411 m a.s.l.; semi-desert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023352. (Fig. 72)

Remarks. The structure of the copulative organs of the examined specimens corresponded to those given by Wunderlich (2011). This species is recorded in Turkey and Azerbaijan (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Silhouettella* Benoit, 1979 from Georgia.

**Oonops pulcher* Templeton, 1835

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1juv.; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7818°, E44.7086°; 629 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 19 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035470 (Fig. 73). – Shida Kartli • 1juv.; Gori, Kvernaki ridge; N41.9834°, E44.1495°; 641m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 8 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035462 • 1♀; N41.9834°, E44.1495°; 641m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 8 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035463 (Fig. 74).

Remarks. This species is readily distinguished from other congeners occurring in the Caucasus by having 4 pairs of long spines on tibia I ventrally (Fig. 73). In the Caucasus, *O. pulcher* is recorded in Azerbaijan and Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

***Orchestina pavesiformis* Saaristo, 2007

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; N41.7573°, E44.7791°; 427 m a.s.l.; bathroom; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025818 • 1♀; N41.7573°, E44.7791°; 427 m a.s.l.; bathroom; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035466 (Figs 75–76) • 1♂; N41.7573°, E44.7791°; 427 m a.s.l.; bathroom; leg. A. Seropian; 24 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035467 (Figs 77–78).

Remarks. *Orchestina pavesiformis* is a tiny spider originating from Europe, known to easily spread by human activity to other continents (Izquierdo and Ramírez 2017; Brescovit et al. 2019). It is the first record of *Orchestina* Simon, 1882 from the Caucasus (WSC 2023). Future studies should reveal whether these findings are the result of recent human activity, or whether these spiders, due to their minuscule size and pale coloration, have gone unnoticed for a long time.

Family Oxyopidae Thorell, 1869

Oxyopes globifer Simon, 1876

GEORGIA – Kakheti reigon • 2♂♂, 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve; N41.214409°, E46.01487°; 460 m a.s.l.; semidesert, shrubs; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Jul. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035871, 1035872, 1035873.

Remarks. This species is reported from North Africa, Spain, the Balkan Peninsula, Turkey, Caucasus (except for Armenia), and Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). A single record in Georgia originates from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is

Figures 72–78. *Silhouettella osmaniye*, male (72: left palp, retrolateral view). *Oonops pulcher* (73: juvenile, leg I, lateral view; 74: female, endogyne, dorsal view). *Orchestina pavesiiformis* (75: female, epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*; 76: endogyne, dorsal view; 77: male, left palp, retrolateral view; 78: same, prolateral view).

the first record of *O. globifer* from the Kakheti region and the second record in the country.

*Palpimanidae Thorell, 1870

**Palpimanus* sp. Dufour, 1820

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀, 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.1249°, E46.6486°; 107 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1035465 (Figs 79, 141), 1035478 (Figs 80–81).

Remarks. It is the first record of Palpimanidae from Georgia. The previous record of *P. sogdianus sensu* Marusik and Guseinov (2003) from Azerbaijan is based on a misidentification and presumably belongs to an undescribed species (Fomichev et al. 2023). Judging by the drawings in Marusik and Guseinov (2003) the specimens from Vashlovani NP presumably belong to the same undescribed species.

Family Philodromidae Thorell, 1870

Philodromus aureolus (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Lagodekhi Mun., Lagodekhi NP; N41.83639°, E 28363°; 800 m a.s.l.; montane beech

forest, vegetation; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2009; KBS 137. Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7441°, E42.0834°; 1264 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, malaise trap; 1 Jun. – 15 Jun. 2021; leg. GGBC (CaBOL) team; CaBOL-ID 1012770.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012770 (BOLD:ACR3732), identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems – *P. aureolus* from Germany (BOLD:ACR3732).

Remarks. A very abundant species in the Caucasus (Otto 2023) with a Palearctic distribution (Nentwit et al. 2023).

Philodromus collinus C.L. Koch, 1835

GEORGIA – Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region • 1♀, 1♂; Ambrolauri Mun., Shaori L.; N42.42243°, E43.11075°; 1100 m a.s.l.; cave; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 178, KVS 325 • 1♂; Tkibuli Mun., NE of Dzirivani Vill.; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest, on branches; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 188.

Remarks. In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Samchablo regions, Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. collinus* from the Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region.

Figures 79–81. *Palpimanus* sp. (79: female, epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*; 80: male, left palp, ventral view; 81: same, retrolateral view).

***Philodromus emarginatus* (Schrank, 1803)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Akhalkalaki Mun., Tabatskuri L.; N41.64434°, E43.59848°; 2000 m a.s.l.; montane pine plantation, on branches; leg. S. Otto; 21 Aug. 2007; KVS 278.

Remarks. Palearctic species (except for North Africa) (WSC 2023). In Georgia, it was known only from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. emarginatus* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

****Philodromus longipalpis* Simon, 1870**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.11100°, E46.64713°; 127 m a.s.l.; Alazani R. bank, tree trunk; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010080. Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N44.7798°, E41.7195°; 440 m a.s.l.; urban area, malaise trap; leg. GGBC (CaBOL) team; 12 – 26 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1021363 (Figs 82–83) • 1♂; N41.7597°, E44.7746°; 428 m a.s.l.; urban area, fence; leg. A. Seropian; 20 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026319 (Figs 84–85). Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Borjomi Mun., Borjomi, E of

Kodiani Vill.; N41.7271°, E43.3773°; 1860 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. B. Thormann, and J. Thormann; 22 Jul. 2019.

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Iberian Peninsula to Azerbaijan and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Azerbaijan. It is the first record of *P. longipalpis* from Georgia.

****Philodromus praedatus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.8025°, E44.6771°; 928 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, stream bank; 9 Jul. 2022; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; CaBOL-ID 1027312 (Fig. 86).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1027312 (BOLD:ACR4121), identical in BOLD Systems to *P. praedatus* from the Netherlands, Switzerland, Bulgaria, and Germany (BOLD:ACR4121).

Remarks. This species is distributed generally in Europe, with records from North Africa (Algeria), Iran, and the Caucasus (Azerbaijan and N Caucasus) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. praedatus* from Georgia.

Figures 82–86. *Philodromus longipalpis* (82: female, epigyne, prepared, ventral view; 83: endogyne, dorsal view; 84: male, left palp, ventral view; 85: tibial apophysis, dorsal view). *Philodromus praedatus*, female (86: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*).

Thanatus arenarius L. Koch, 1872

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Kaspi Mun., Kodistskaro Vill.; N42.0279°, E44.3575°; 795 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 3 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026334.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1026334 (BOLD:AAP3048), identical in BOLD Systems to *T. arenarius* from Bulgaria (BOLD:AAP3048, *p*-distance 0.77%).

Remarks. This species is widely distributed in the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (but see Logunov and Huseynov 2008 for Azerbaijan). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Samachablo region and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. arenarius* from the Shida Kartli region.

Thanatus formicinus (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., NE of Poladaantkari Vill.; N41.60837°, E44.99576°; 400 m a.s.l.; shrub steppe; leg. S. Otto; 22 Mar. 2009; KVS 349. Tbilisi • 1♂; Kojori; N41.6794°, E44.7078°; 1000 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010362.

Genetics. A single barcode obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010362 (BOLD:AAL7639) is identical in BOLD Systems to *T. formicinus* from Slovenia (BOLD:AAL7639).

Remarks. This species is widely distributed in the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (but see Logunov and Huseynov 2008 for Azerbaijan). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Samtskhe-Javakheti, Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti, Guria, Samachablo regions, and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. formicinus* from the Kvemo Kartli region.

Thanatus imbecillus L. Koch, 1878

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Vere Valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 27 Apr. 2009; KVS 376 • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7806°, E44.1075°; 775 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 3 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010396. Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP; N41.1394°, E46.5808°; 213 m a.s.l.; steppe, Lekistskali (Mlshetskali) R. bank, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010002.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010002 and 1010396 (BOLD:AAQ0164). There are no barcodes of *T. imbecillus* available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones. The nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems is *Thanatus* sp. from Turkey with an Early-Release status, which given the mean *p*-distance of 0.98% to our specimens is likely to be *T. imbecillus* also.

Remarks. The species is distributed from the Balkan Peninsula to Central Asia and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). A very abundant species distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023).

Family Pholcidae C.L. Koch, 1850

Spermophora senoculata (Dugès, 1836)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7574°, E44.7791°; 455 m a.s.l.; bathroom; leg. A. Seropian; 3 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010398 • 1♂; N41.7574°, E44.7791°; 455 m a.s.l.; bathroom; leg. A. Seropian; 7 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010432. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.3600°, E43.7107°; 2223 m a.s.l.; Abuli forest, leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 28 Sep. 2019; CaBOL-ID 1012765. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Mtskheta Mun., Shiomghvime; N41.8619°, E44.6404°; 700 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035800.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010398 and 1010432 (BOLD:AAI0113) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *S. senoculata* from Greece (BOLD:AAI0113, mean *p*-distance 0.31%),

Remarks. A common species in the Caucasus, lacking records from Armenia (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). In Georgia, it was previously reported from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

Family Phrurolithidae Banks, 1892

Phrurolithus festivus (C.L. Koch, 1835)

GEORGIA – Guria region • 1♂; Ozurgeti Mun., Gaghma Dvabzu Vill.; N41.93438°, E42.05894°; 200 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. G. Makharadze; 20 Apr. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004190. Kakheti • 3♀♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025554, 1025682, 1025683. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Akhalkalaki Mun., Bozali Vill.; N41.2714°, E43.3379°; 1866m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 6 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025772.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1004190 (BOLD:AFH3455) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. festivus* from Canada (BOLD:AFH3455, *p*-distance 2.56%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, introduced to Canada (WSC 2023). It is an abundant species distributed throughout the whole Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, this species was previously recorded from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti, Samachablo, Adjara, and Abkhazia regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. festivus* from the Guria, Kakheti, and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

Family Salticidae Blackwall, 1841

Aelurillus concolor Kulczyński, 1891

GEORGIA – Samtskhe Javakheti region • 3♂♂; Akhaltsikhe Mun., Uraveli Gorge; N41.6145°, E43.0371°; 986

m a.s.l.; steppe, rocky slopes; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 10 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1018752, 1018753, 1018754. Tbilisi • 3♂♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7775°, E44.7056°; 664 m a.s.l.; steppe, slopes with loose soil; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 17 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1016828, 1016829, 1016830. Kakheti • 3♂♂; Kvareli Mun., Sabue Vill.; N42.0566°, E45.1232°; 634 m a.s.l.; Ilto R. bank, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1025768, 1025769, 1025770.

Genetics. Three nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016828, 1016829, 1016830, 1025768, 1025769, and 1025770 (BOLD:AFH1833) (mean *p*-distance 0.73%). The maximum *p*-distance between populations from Dighomi Village (mean *p*-distance 0.1%) and Sabue Village (mean *p*-distance 0.81%) was 1.06%. There are no barcodes of *A. concolor* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. This species distribution ranges from Greece to Central Asia and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is a very abundant species with no records from Armenia (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). In Georgia, *A. concolor* is known only from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from the Samtskhe-Javakheti and Kakheti regions.

**Aelurillus m-nigrum* Kulczyński, 1891

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 3♂♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.98555°, E44.13428°; 713 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1010363, 1020272 (Figs 87–88), 1020273.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020272 and 1020273 (BOLD:AFG9897) (mean *p*-distance 0.3%). There are no barcodes of *A. m-nigrum* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. Distributed from SE Europe east to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously known only from Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. m-nigrum* from Georgia.

Aelurillus v-insignitus (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Adigeni Mun., Triala L.; N41.6412°, E42.7007°; 1625 m a.s.l.; mixed-forest edge; leg. G. Iankoshvili; 9 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018708 • 1♂; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3760°, E43.2754°; 1247 m a.s.l.; steppe, xerothermic slope; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018709.

Remarks. Species with Palaearctic distribution (except for North Africa) (Nentwig et al. 2023) is widespread throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Shida Kartli, Racha-Lechkhumi regions, and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. v-insignitus* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

Asianellus festivus (C.L. Koch, 1834)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂, 1♀, 1juv; Akhaltsikhe Mun., Atskuri Vill.; N41.72819°, E43.16514°; 1000

Figures 87–94. *Aelurillus m-nigrum*, male (87: left palp, ventral view; 88: same, retrolateral view). *Attulus ammophilus*, male (89: left palp, ventral view; 90: same, retrolateral view). *Attulus rupicola*, female (91: endogyne, dorsal view). *Attulus saltator*, male (92: left palp, ventral view; 93: same, retrolateral view). *Bianor albobimaculatus*, female (94: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*).

m a.s.l.; xerothermic pasture; leg. S. Otto; 5 Apr. 2009; KVS 370. Tbilisi • 1♂, Tbilisi; N41.7691°, E44.7634°; 446 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Mar. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023280.

Remarks. Species with Palaearctic distribution (except for North Africa, Turkey, and Iran) (Nentwig et al. 2023) is widespread throughout the whole Caucasus (Otto 2023).

****Attulus ammophilus* (Thorell, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.98586°, E44.10920°; 600 m a.s.l.; xerothermic southern slope, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 7 Apr. 2009; KBS 199. Tbilisi • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.80623°, E44.68700°; 940 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010403 (Figs 89–90). Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Kazbegi Mun.; N42.586°, E44.43°; 2177 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 3 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TIS-8008011 • 1♂; Mna Valley; N42.58°, E44.47°; 2010 m a.s.l.; leg. H.-J. Krammer; 3 Jul. 2019; ID 8008101. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂, 1juv.; Gardabani Mun., Kumisi Vill.; N41.5878°, E44.8594°; 486 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, on ground; leg. Seropian A., Bulbulashvili N., Zukakishvili A.; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020859, 102086 • 1♂; Bolnisi Mun., Tandzia Vill.; N41.4523°, E44.3605°; 915 m a.s.l.; forest edge, on ground; leg. Bulbulashvili N.; 16 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035762.

Remarks. It is an east Mediterranean–Central Asian species, recorded from Turkey and Ukraine in the west, the Caucasus (except for Georgia) and Iran, to Kyrgyzstan and Afghanistan in the east, and introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *A. ammophilus* from Georgia.

***Attulus damini* (Chyzer, 1891)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Zugdidi Mun., Kolkheti NP; N42.33802°, E41.61131°; 0 m a.s.l.; sea coast; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 2 Aug. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1030865.

Remarks. The examined specimen is the third record of this species in the Caucasus – previous records are from Krasnodar Krai of Russia and Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region. The general distribution of *A. damini* is Pontic with a record from Croatia (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Attulus penicillatus* (Simon, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Bolnisi Mun., Tandzia Vill.; N41.4523°, E44.3605°; 915 m a.s.l.; forest edge, on ground; leg. Bulbulashvili N.; 16 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035763.

Remarks. Distributed from France to Japan (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is

known from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Kakheti regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. penicillatus* from the Kvemo Kartli region.

***Attulus relictarius* (Logunov, 1998)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Kaspi Mun., Khovle Vill.; N41.8840°, E44.2510°; 1069 m a.s.l.; meadow, mixed forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1011727 • 1♀; Gori Mun., Gori; N41.97702, E44.08040; edge of deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Sep. 2020; KBS 368. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.43702°, E43.30781°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032732. Kakheti • 1♀; Signnaghi Mun., Erisimedi Vill.; N41.5944, E46.3319; 193 m a.s.l.; leg. G. Iankoshvili; 11 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020892.

Remarks. *Attulus relictarius* is endemic to the Caucasus (WSC 2023), recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Kakheti, Adjara, Abkhazia, and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions). It is the first record of this species from the Shida Kartli region.

****Attulus rupicola* (C.L. Koch, 1837)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., NW of Akhmeta, Aniskhevi R.; N42.0830°, E45.3004°; 1022 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025806 (Fig. 91).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1025806 (BOLD:AFH3371) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. rupicola* from Switzerland (BOLD:ACA5322, *p*-distance 2.78%).

Remarks. Distributed from Spain to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus there were two doubtful records (no illustrations provided) of this species from Chechnya (Minoranski 1988). It is the first record of *A. rupicola* from Georgia and South Caucasus.

****Attulus saltator* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1868)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀ (subadult); Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3760°, E43.2754°; 1247 m a.s.l.; xerothermic steppe slope; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011146. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9870°, E44.1562°; 667 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, rocky slopes; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023807 (Figs 92–93). Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Mtskheta Mun., Saskhori Vill.; N41.8458°, E44.5251°; 634 m a.s.l.; steppe, rocky slopes; leg. A. Seropian; 30 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023808.

Genetics. Three barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011146, 1023807 and 1023808 (BOLD:AAZ7729, mean *p*-distance 1.01%) have the same match in BOLD Systems with barcodes of *A. saltator* from Finland with Private status (mean *p*-distance 0.56%) and barcodes of *A. penicilloides* (Wesołowska, 1981) from Germany (BOLD:AAZ7729, mean *p*-distance 0.56%). *Attulus penicilloides* was described by a single female from North Korea and *A. saltator* is a species widely distributed in Eu-

rope (e.g., in Germany) it's clear that all European barcodes of *A. penicilloides* should be ascribed to *A. saltator*.

Remarks. This species has a Palearctic distribution (except for North Africa, Iran, and East Asia) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from Dagestan and Karachay-Cherkessia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *A. saltator* from Georgia.

****Bianor albobimaculatus* (Lucas, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.63903°, E45.01393°; 460 m a.s.l.; reed; leg. S. Otto; 8 Sep. 2006; KVS 5. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Zugdidi Mun., Kolkheti NP; N42.33802°, E41.61131°; 1 m a.s.l.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 2 Aug. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1030866 (Fig. 94).

Remarks. Distributed from South Africa to the Mediterranean, NE to Central Asia, with records from India and Nepal (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Bianor* G. W. Peckham & E. G. Peckham 1886 from Georgia.

****Chalcoscirtus tanasevichi* Marusik, 1991**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareji monster vicinity; N41.45672°, E45.35958°; 720 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010392 (Fig. 95). Tbilisi • 1♀ (subadult); Dighomi Vill.; N41.45672°, E45.35958°; 730 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, xerothermic slope; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1004204.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010392 (BOLD:AFH3421) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. nigritus* (Thorell, 1875) from Russia with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 5.86%). There are no barcodes of *C. tanasevichi* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. Distributed from Turkey east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). This species is most closely related to *C. nigritus* (Thorell, 1875) from which it can be distinguished by the larger embolic coil and longer tibial apophysis. In the Caucasus, *C. tanasevichi* was previously reported in Azerbaijan, Armenia, and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

****Cyrba algerina* (Lucas, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.43702°, E43.30781°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018683 (Fig. 96). Kvemo Kartli • 1♀, 1♂; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681, E44.8219; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020881, 1020890.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018683 (BOLD:AAM9266) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. algerina* from unknown location (BOLD:AAM9266, *p*-distance 1.79%).

Figures 95–103. *Chalcoscirtus tanasevichi*, male (95: tibial apophysis, retrolateral view). *Cyrba algerina*, female (96: endogyne, dorsal view). *Cyrba ocellata*, male (97: left palp, ventral view). *Icius hamatus*, male (98: left palp, ventral view; 99: same, retrolateral view). *Leptorchestes berolinensis*, male (100: left palp, ventral view). *Mogrus neglectus* (101: left palp, ventral view; 102: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*; 103: endogyne, dorsal view).

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded in Azerbaijan and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Cyrba* Simon, 1876 from Georgia.

****Cyrba ocellata* (Kroneberg, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂; Tbilisi; N41.75927°, E44.77949°; 428 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. A. Seropian; 20 May 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1004196 (Fig. 97), 1004197. Kakheti • 1♂ (subadult); Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachu-

na Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.27894°, E45.89319°; 277 m a.s.l.; under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 18 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010006 • 1♀; Lagodekhi Mun., Heretiskari Vill.; N41.711°, E46.087°; 200 m a.s.l., grave; leg. T. Klug; 9 Jul. 2019.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010006, 1026984 (BOLD:ACR0186) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. ocellata* from India with Private status (*p*-distance 1.69%).

Remarks. Species with a very wide and disjunct range, encompassing Eastern Africa, the Caucasus, Central Asia,

and Indo-China, introduced to Australia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously reported from Azerbaijan and Dagestan (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Dendryphantes rudis* (Sundevall, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Gandzani Vill.; N41.3554°, E43.6984°; 2313 m a.s.l.; leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 19 Aug. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012772.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012772 (BOLD:AAY5220) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *D. rudis* from Austria (BOLD:AAY5220, *p*-distance 1.22%).

Remarks. This species has a Palearctic distribution (except for North Africa, Iran, and East Asia). In Georgia, it was previously recorded from Tbilisi and the Samachablo region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *D. rudis* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Euophrys frontalis* (Walckenaer, 1802)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Martvili Mun., Tekhuri R. gorge; N42.5992°, E42.3470°; 411 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1030857. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Mtskheta Mun., Shiomghvime; N41.8619°, E44.6404°; 700m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035798.

Remarks. Palearctic species, known from numerous localities in Georgia and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region.

***Evarcha michailovi* Logunov, 1992**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.99245°, E44.15016°; 767 m a.s.l.; steppe, on Cirsium sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 30 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010263 • 1♂(sub); N41.99245°, E44.15016°; 767 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Jun. 2021 (matured on 30 Jun. 2021); CaBOL-ID 1010291. Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7812°, E44.7024°; 734 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. G. Makharadze; 17 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012922.

Remarks. Palearctic species (except for North Africa, most of Central Europe, and Iran) (Nentwig et al. 2023). Previously this species was known in Georgia from Sinaguri (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *E. michailovi* from Tbilisi and the Shida Kartli region.

****Heliophanus lineiventris* Simon, 1868**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9807°, E44.0926°; 584 m a.s.l.; floodplain; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012356 • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki ridge; N41.9834°, E44.1495°; 641 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 4 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035464.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012356 (BOLD:AAZ7819) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. lineiventris* with Private status from Russia (*p*-distance 1.08%).

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed from the Iberian Peninsula to East Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously reported from Armenia and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia.

***Heliophanus melinus* L. Koch, 1867**

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681°, E44.8219°; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020886.

Remarks. Palearctic species, distributed in the Mediterranean, Balkan Peninsula, Turkey, the Caucasus, CE and SE Russia (Nentwig et al. 2023). Previously this species was known in Georgia from Tbilisi and the Mtskheta-Mtianeti region (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Kvemo Kartli region.

***Heliophanus mordax* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Vere Valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 31 May 2009; KVS 421.

Remarks. It is an eastern Mediterranean–Central Asian species recorded from Ukraine, SE Russia, the Caucasus, Afghanistan, and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the second record from Georgia.

*****Icius hamatus* (C.L. Koch, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.72960°, E44.79589°; 533 m a.s.l.; Syringa bush; leg. A. Seropian; 2 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010292 • 1♂; N41.72960°, E44.79589°; 533 m a.s.l.; Syringa bush; leg. A. Seropian; 9 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010414 (Figs 98–99).

Remarks. Species with Ponto-Mediterranean distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Icius* Simon, 1876 from the Caucasus.

****Leptorchestes berolinensis* (C.L. Koch, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9801°, E44.1907°; 611 m a.s.l.; steppe, rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023933 (Fig. 100) • 1♀; N41.98130°, E44.07880°; 603 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011735 • 1♀; N41.98130°, E44.07880°; 603 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012388. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill; N41.43702°, E43.30781°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018768.

Genetics. Four identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011735, 1012388, 1018768, and 1023933 (BOLD:AFH3261). Identification via COI

subunit barcode was not straightforward: the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *L. sikorskii* Prószyński, 2000 from Bulgaria with Private status (*p*-distance 1.7%). The second best match is *L. beroliensis* from Bulgaria (BOLD:ABA8705, *p*-distance 3.23%).

Remarks. Distributed from the Iberian Peninsula to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously reported from Azerbaijan and Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

Marpissa pomatia (Walckenaer, 1802)

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♂; Poti Mun., Kolkheti NP; N of Pichori R.; N42.14758°, E41.82526°; 0 m a.s.l.; grass; leg. S. Otto; 17 May 2009; KVS 397.

Remarks. Palearctic species, in the Caucasus recorded only from Georgia (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023).

Mendoza canestrinii (Ninni, 1868)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.63903°, E45.01393°; 460 m a.s.l.; reed; leg. S. Otto; 8 Sep. 2006; KVS 3. Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Ispani II wetland; N41.86339°, E41.78367°; 6 m a.s.l.; Sphagnum bog, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 22 May 2009; KVS 408. Shida Kartli • 2♂♂, 1♀; Kaspi Mun., Kodistskaro Vill.; N42.0170°, E44.3517°; 709 m a.s.l.; floodplain, Arundo sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012395, 1012419, 1012431.

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean to East Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). All previous records of this species in Georgia (Otto 2023) originate from the western part of the country. It is the first record from the Kvemo Kartli and Shida Kartli regions.

**Mogrus neglectus* (Simon, 1868)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♀, 1juv.; Gardabani Mun., Kumisi Vill.; N41.59954°, E44.84175°; 530 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. A. Seropian; 7 Jun. 2019; CaBOL-ID 1004195 (Figs 101–102). Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2758°, E45.8877°; 268 m a.s.l.; semidesert, Tamarix sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023331 (Fig. 103).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1004195 (BOLD:AFH1320). There are no barcodes of *M. neglectus* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. Species with a Palearctic distribution, known from the Balkan Peninsula, Greece, Turkey, the Caucasus (NW Caucasus, Azerbaijan), Cyprus, Israel, Iran, and Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Mogrus* Simon, 1882 from Georgia.

Myrmarachne formicaria (De Geer, 1778)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 2♀♀, 1♂; Kaspi Mun., Kodistskaro; N42.0174°, E44.3495°; 712 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari

R. floodplain, Arundo sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 25 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012393, 1012405, 1012417. Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Kumisi Vill; N41.6027°, E44.8163°; 494 m a.s.l.; Phragmites thicket; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016826. Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.0722°, E45.3900°; 431 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, meadow; leg. Cabol team; 27 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 10301236.

Genetics. Three identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012405, 1012417, and 1016826 (BOLD:ABA9498) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. formicaria* from Germany (BOLD:ABA9498, *p*-distance 0.62%).

Remarks. Species with a Holarctic distribution (introduced to North America) (Nentwig et al. 2023). Distributed throughout the Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Shida Kartli region.

Neaetha absheronica Logunov & Guseinov, 2002

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi, N41.76991°, E44.76664°; 450 m a.s.l.; colline, Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 30 Apr. 2020, CaBOL-ID 1004203.

Remarks. Species with a Caucaso-Eastern Mediterranean distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus recorded in Azerbaijan and Georgia (Abkhazia region). It is the first record from Tbilisi and the second in Georgia (Otto 2023).

Neon rayi (Simon, 1875)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 385. Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; 628 m a.s.l.; meadow, Carpinus orientalis leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020755.

Remarks. Distributed in South and Central Europe, the Caucasus, Central Asia, and Israel (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus recorded in Azerbaijan and Georgia (Kakheti region). It is the first record from Tbilisi and the second in Georgia (Otto 2023).

**Pellenes diagonalis* (Simon, 1868)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂; Vere Valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 27 Apr. 2009; KVS 377 • 1♂; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 1 May 2009; KBS 202 • 2♂♂, 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.78308°, E44.70042°; 728 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 20 Oct. 2019 (male adult 20 Mar. 2020, female adult 2 May 2020); CaBOL-IDs 1004187 (Fig. 104), 1004188, 1004189 • 1♀; N41.75488°, E44.75165°; 593 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 21 Jul. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1010025. Shida Kartli • 1juv; Kaspi Mun., Nichbisi Vill.; N41.8426°, E44.5310°; 700 m

Figures 104–112. *Pellenes diagonalis*, male (104: left palp, ventral view). *Pellenes geniculatus*, female (105: endogyne, dorsal view). *Phlegra cinereofasciata*, male (106: left palp, ventral view; 107: same, retrolateral view). *Plexippoides gestroi*, female (108: endogyne, dorsal view). *Pseudeuphrys vafra*, male (109: left palp, ventral view; 110: same, retrolateral view). *Saitis tauricus*, male (111: left palp, ventral view; 112: same, retrolateral view).

a.s.l.; meadow, sweeping; leg. CaBOL team; 30 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032342.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004187 and 1004189 (BOLD:AFH2216) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. diagonalis* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (p -distance 1.71%).

Remarks. Species with a Caucaso-Eastern Mediterranean distribution, recorded in Israel and Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from Azerbaijan and Armenia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia (Otto 2023).

***Pellenes epularis* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂, 2juv; Akhaltsikhe Mun., Atskuri Vill.; N41.72819°, E43.16514°; 1000 m a.s.l.; xerothermic pasture, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 5 Apr.

2009; KVS 371. – Tbilisi • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8000°, E44.6824°; 874 m a.s.l.; forest edge, rocky slope; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021074. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Bolnisi Mun., Tandzia Vill.; N41.4523°, E44.3605°; 915 m a.s.l.; forest edge; leg. Bulbulashvili N.; 16 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035761.

Remarks. Species with a disjunct distribution, known from South Africa, and from Greece east to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Samtskhe-Javakheti region, Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Kvemo Kartli region.

****Pellenes geniculatus* (Simon, 1868)**

GEORGIA Tbilisi – • 1♀; Vashlijvari; N41.75488°, E44.75176°; 617 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. A. Seropian; 20 Aug. 2020; KVS 559; CaBOL-ID 1004208 (Fig. 105) • 1♀;

N41.75488°, E44.75165°; 593 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 21 Jul. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1012521 • 1♀; N41.75488°, E44.75165°; 593 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 21 Jun. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1010025. Kakheti • 1♀; Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2764°, E45.8884°; 273 m a.s.l.; semidesert, light trap; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL ID 1032685.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1004208 (BOLD:AAZ9048) identical in BOLD Systems to *P. geniculatus* with Private status from Russia.

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, Russia (Dagestan), and Armenia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

Pellenes nigrociliatus (Simon, 1875)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 5♂♂; Gardabani Mun., NE of Poladaantkari Vill.; N41.60837°, E44.99576°; 400 m a.s.l.; shrub steppe; leg. S. Otto; 22 Mar. 2009; KVS 352. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9771°, E44.0984°; 589 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012541. Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareji monastery vicinity; N41.4567°, E45.3596°; 720 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 8 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010380.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010380 (BOLD:AAZ9048) identical in BOLD Systems to *P. nigrociliatus* with Private status from Russia.

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Kvemo Kartli, Kakheti, and Shida Kartli regions and the second from Georgia.

Pellenes seriatus (Thorell, 1875)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N° 41.7828, E44.7005°; 775 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, rocks; leg. A. Seropian, 24 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010408.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010408 (BOLD:AFH2081) with the nearest neighbors in BOLD Systems *P. seriatus* from Bulgaria and *P. tripunctatus* (Walckenaer, 1802) from Germany, both with a Private Status. Identification via CO1 subunit barcode was not straightforward despite pronounced differences in morphology, especially in the males of these two species.

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean east to Central Asia and south to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A common species distributed throughout the whole Caucasus. It is the first record from Tbilisi and the second from Georgia (Otto 2023).

**Phlegra cinereofasciata* (Simon, 1868)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂, 1♀; Vashlijvari; N41.75488°, E44.75176°; 617 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 20 Aug. 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1004192 (Figs 106–107), 1004193, 1004194.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004192 and 1004193 (BOLD:AFH2913) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. cinereofasciata* from France with a private status (*p*-distance 3.26%).

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean to China (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, Armenia, and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean east to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan, Russia (Dagestan), and Armenia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

**Plexippoides gestroi* (Dalmás, 1920)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♀♀; Tbilisi; N41.72991°, E44.79641°; 400 m a.s.l.; wall; leg. A. Seropian; 1 Jul. 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1004205, 1004206. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Pantishara Gorge; N41.24005°, E46.38471°; 528 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010081 (Fig. 108).

Remarks. This species is recorded in the eastern Mediterranean, Caucasus, Iran, and Iraq (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from Azerbaijan (Guseinov 1999 (misidentified as *P. starmuehlneri* (junior synonym of *P. flavescens*) (Logunov 2021)). It is the first record of *Plexippoides* Prószyński, 1984 from Georgia.

**Pseudeuophrys obsoleta* (Simon, 1868)

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareji monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.0391°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 386.

Remarks. Distributed in the Mediterranean, Caucasus, Central Europe, Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Pseudeuophrys vafra* (Blackwall, 1867)

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♂; Senaki Mun., SE of Senaki; N42.26500°, E42.08583°; 20 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 25 Sep. 2011; KVS 303. Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.75737°, E44.77898°; 427 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. A. Seropian; 24 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016884 (Figs 109–110) • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.7124°, E44.7485°; 495 m a.s.l.; building; leg. B. Chitadze; 11 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012898.

Genetics. Two barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016884 and 1012898 (BOLD:AFH2167, *p*-distance 1.01%). There are no barcodes of *P. vafra* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. It is the first record of this species from the Caucasus (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). The nearest known record of *P. vafra* is 940 km NE in Ukraine, Crimean Peninsula (Logunov 1998).

Pseudicius encarpatus (Walckenaer, 1802)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • ♂; Tbilisi; N41.7629°, E44.7725°; 437 m a.s.l.; suburban; leg. A. Seropian, 24 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012487, 1012535

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012487 (BOLD:AAY8456) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. encarpatus* from Germany (BOLD:AAY8456, *p*-distance 0.77%).

Remarks. Distributed from Europe to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known from N Caucasus, Azerbaijan, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Kakheti regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Tbilisi and the third in Georgia.

*****Saitis tauricus* Kulczyński, 1904**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N41.759269°, E44.779494°; 400 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Apr. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004201 (Figs 111–112) • 1♀ (subadult); N41.759269°, E44.779494°; 400 m a.s.l.; apartment; leg. A. Seropian; 15 Apr. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004202 • 1♂; N41.7124°, E44.7485°; 495 m a.s.l.; building; leg. B. Chitadze, 11 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1022954.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004201 and 1004202 (BOLD:AAL7842), identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *S. tauricus* from Bulgaria (BOLD:AAL7842).

Remarks. Material from Tbilisi represents the first record of *Saitis* Simon, 1876 to the Caucasus. *Saitis tauricus* could have been imported several times with goods from the Crimean Peninsula, as our findings in two consecutive years and the very recent observations in iNaturalist from Georgia could also indicate an established population in Tbilisi.

****Salticus tricinctus* (C.L. Koch, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.27895°, E45.89319°; 285 m a.s.l.; semidesert, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 18 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010071 (Figs 113–114). Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂ (subadult); Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.43702°, E43.30781°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, on rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018627.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018627 (BOLD:AFH3586). There are no barcodes of *S. tricinctus* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. *Salticus tricinctus* is recorded in the eastern Mediterranean, Caucasus, Iran, Kazakhstan, and Afghanistan (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from numerous localities (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *S. tricinctus* from Georgia.

****Sibianor turkestanicus* Logunov, 2001**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., SW of Gremi Vill. (Kakheti region); N42.00272°, E45.65850°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic shrubland, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 1 Apr. 2009; KVS 366.

Remarks. This species is known from Kyrgyzstan and Azerbaijan (Logunov 2001; WSC 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

****Synageles dalmaticus* (Keyserling, 1863)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.73118°, E44.79466°; 436 m a.s.l.; Ficus carica; leg. A. Seropian; 28 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010344 (Figs 115–116) • 1♀; N41.7596°, E44.7681°; 435 m a.s.l.; Ficus carica; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025669.

Remarks. This species is known from the Mediterranean, Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Russia (Europe), and Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, *S. dalmaticus* is recorded in Azerbaijan and Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Synageles venator* (Lucas, 1836)**

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Mestia Mun., SW of Ushguli Vill.; N42.8836°, E43.057416°; 1100 m a.s.l.; in grass; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KVS 345. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori. Kvernaki ridge; N41.7596°, E44.1907°; 435 m a.s.l.; rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023937.

Remarks. Species with a wide Palaearctic distribution, introduced to North America (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from N Caucasus and Georgia (Imereti and Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Shida Kartli region.

Family Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872

***Olios sericeus* (Kroneberg, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli region • 1♂ (subadult); Gori; N41.9781°, E44.1068°; 591 m a.s.l.; wall; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 9 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011618. Kvemo Kartli • 1♂, 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden; leg. S. Otto; 25 May 2009; Janashia Museum Tbilisi (coll. no. B1-01) • 1♂; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden; leg. S. Otto; 1 Jun. 2007; KVS 287 • 1♂; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden; leg. T. Shetekauri; 1 Jun. 2008; KVS 346.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011618 (BOLD:AFH0690). There are no barcodes of *O. sericeus* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. This species has a Central Asian-Caucasian distribution with records from Iran and Afghanistan (Nentwig et al. 2023). Jäger and Otto (2007) recorded this species in Georgia from Rodionovka Vill. The examined material indicates a more widespread distribution of this species in the country.

Family Tetragnathidae Menge, 1866

***Meta bourneti* Simon, 1922**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 2♀♀; Dedoplistskaro, Artsviskheoba Gorge (Eagle Gorge); N41.4895°, E46.0967°; 751 m a.s.l.; cave; leg. A. Sanakoeva and A. Seropian; 21 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1010078, 1010383.

Figures 113–116. *Salticus tricinctus*, male (**113**: left palp, ventral view; **114**: preserved specimen, dorsal view). *Synageles dalmaticus*, female (**115**: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*; **116**: preserved specimen, dorsal view).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010078 (BOLD:AAO1855) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. bournetii* from Germany (BOLD:AAO1855, *p*-distance 0.18%).

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A troglophile species known in the Caucasus from Georgia only, in caves of Abkhazia (Otto 2023). The findings from Artsiviskheoba Gorge are the southeasternmost record in Georgia and the first one from the Kakheti region. Two more photographic observations of this species in Georgian Biodiversity Database (Tarkhishvili et al. 2013) by Vasil Gabunia and Giorgi Sheklashvili from caves near Mujireti and Dzegvi villages indicate a wider distribution of *M. bournetii* within the country.

***Metellina mingei* (Blackwall, 1869)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Borjomi Mun., Bakuriani; N41.74874°, E43.52424°; 1700 m a.s.l.; montane forest; leg. S. Otto; 22 Aug. 2007 (adult 25 Sep. 2007); KVS

25. Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region • 1♂; Tkibuli Mun., Nakerala Ridge; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest, branches; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 188.

Remarks. Species with a wide Palaearctic distribution range (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). Distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Azerbaijan). In Georgia, it is known from the Kakheti region and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samtskhe-Javakheti and Racha-Lechkhumi regions.

***Metellina merianae* (Scopoli, 1763)**

GEORGIA – Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region • 2♂♂, 7♀♀; Tsageri Mun., NW of Tvishi; N42.52333°, E42.73389°; 300 m a.s.l.; old mining gallery; leg. F. Walther; 8 Oct. 2011; KVS 302. Kakheti • 2♀♀; Dedoplistskaro, Artsiviskheoba Gorge (Eagle Gorge); N41.4895°, E46.0967°; 751 m a.s.l.; in cave; leg. A. Sanakoeva & A. Seropian; 21 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1010008, 1010070.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010070 (BOLD:AAE7901) nearly identical to the COI gene of the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. merianae* from Germany BOLD:AAE7901, *p*-distance 0.17%).

Remarks. Species with a wide Palaearctic distribution range (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). Distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia). It is the first record from the Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region.

Metellina segmentata (Clerck, 1757)

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 6♂♂, 4♀♀; Dusheti Mun., W of Chargali Vill., Pshavi-Arakvi Valley; N42.32447°, E44.89368°; 1000 m a.s.l.; montane shrubs; leg. S. Otto; 30 Aug. 2006; KVS 13, KBS 10. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♀♀; Borjomi Mun., Tsaghveri; N41.80350°, E43.48135°; 1000 m a.s.l.; leg. F. Walther; 17 Sep. 2011; KBS 152 • 1♂; Kvishkheti, Mtkvari R.; N41.9613°, E43.5116°; 723 m a.s.l.; floodplain, river bank, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 8 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018750.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018750 (BOLD:AAD1127), identical in BOLD Systems to COI genes of *M. segmentata* from Germany, Norway, Slovenia, Canada, and Austria (BOLD:AAD1127).

Remarks. A very abundant Palaearctic species, introduced to North America (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). Distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023).

Pachygnatha clercki Sundevall, 1823

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♀♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Bugdasheni Managed Reserve, Bugdasheni L.; N41.1985°, E43.6884°; 2042 m a.s.l.; lake shore, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018770, 1018771.

Genetics. Two barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1018770 (BOLD:AAC2188) and 1018771 (BOLD:AFH3979) (*p*-distance 1.22%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. clercki* from Canada (BOLD:AAC2188, mean *p*-distance 0.77%).

Remarks. Species with a Holarctic distribution range (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). A common species in the Caucasus, recorded from N Caucasus and Georgia (Kakheti, Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti, and Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti regions). It is the first record of *P. clercki* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

Pachygnatha degeeri Sundevall, 1830

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7695°, E44.7737°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 15 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016894. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Ninotsminda Mun., Saghamo L.; N41.2941°, E43.7309°; 2006 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018626 • 1♂; Madatapa Managed Reserve; N41.1968°,

E43.7587°; 2128 m a.s.l.; meadow, under stone; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018653 • 1♂, 3♀♀; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3529°, E43.2518°; 1315 m a.s.l.; steppe, Mtkvari R. bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1032703, 1032704, 1032705, 1032706. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Khashuri Mun., Kvishkheti Vill.; N41.9613°, E43.5116°; 723 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. bank, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 8 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018695.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016894 and 1018695 (BOLD:AAP5593, *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. degeeri* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (mean *p*-distance 0.85%). The second nearest neighbor is *P. degeeri* from France (BOLD:ABY9214, mean *p*-distance 2.39%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023) distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti, Adjara, and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *P. degeeri* from Tbilisi, Samtskhe-Javakheti, and Shida Kartli regions.

Pachygnatha listeri Sundevall, 1830

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Tianeti Mun., Orkhevi Vill.; N41.9743°, E45.0252°; 1009 m a.s.l.; Iori R. bank; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025824.

Remarks. Palaearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023) distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Adjara, Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti, Kakheti, and Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti regions. It is the first record of *P. listeri* from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti region.

Family Theridiidae Sundevall, 1833

Anelosimus vittatus (C.L. Koch, 1836)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Kareli Mun., Kintsvi Vill.; N41.9611°, E43.8370°; 1043 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 17 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026381.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1026381 (BOLD:AAK0768) nearly identical in BOLD Systems to *A. vittatus* from Germany (BOLD:AAK0768, *p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species with distribution range from the Mediterranean west to Iran and north to Scandinavia (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *A. vittatus* from the Shida Kartli region (Otto 2023).

***Coscinida tibialis* Simon, 1895

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂, 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.81156°, E44.68843°; 850 m, a.s.l.; montane, broad-leaved forest, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Nov. 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1004224 (Figs 117–118), 1004225 (Fig. 119). Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9673°, E44.1195°; 593 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020736. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Tsalenjikha

Figures 117–121. *Coscinida tibialis* (117: male, left palp, ventral view; 118: same, retrolateral view; 119: female, epigyne, ventral view). *Crustulina sticta*, male (120: left palp, retrolateral view). *Dipoenia torva*, male (121: left palp, retrolateral view).

Mun., Skuri; N42.6880°, E42.1606°; 437 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027652.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004224 and 1004225 (BOLD:AFH3594) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. tibialis* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (p -distance 1.7%).

Remarks. This species has a disjunctive distribution and is known from southern Europe, the Middle East, and Africa (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *Coscinida* Simon, 1895 from the Caucasus. The specimens from Telovani village had a strikingly orange coloration, while others – ground pale.

Crustulina guttata (Wider, 1834)

GEORGIA – Guria region • 1♂, 1juv; Ozurgeti Mun., Gaghma Dvabzu Vill.; N41.93438°, E42.05894°; 14. – 22 Apr. 2020; leg. G. Makharadze; KVS 366. Kakheti • 1♂, 1♀; Sagarejo Mun., Gombori Pass; N41.86492°,

E45.27787°; 1600 m a.s.l.; pasture; leg. S. Otto; 1 Apr. 2009; KBS 104 • 1♀; David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KBS 204. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9771°, E44.0984°; 589 m a.s.l.; dry steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012542. Tbilisi • 1♀, 1♂, Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 789 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020803, 1020804 • 1♂, Telovani Vill.; N41.8016°, E44.6789°; 913 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 7 Jan. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1020719.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012542 (BOLD:AFH2082) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. guttata* from Turkey (BOLD:AAO1658, p -distance 0.31%).

Remarks. Species with a Palearctic distribution (except for North Africa and Turkey) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is known from the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Guria, Kakheti, Shida Kartli regions, and Tbilisi.

****Crustulina sticta* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1861)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.77744°, E44.70509°, alt. 673 m a.s.l.; mossy slope, under rock; leg. A. Seropian; 28 Oct. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1004191 (Fig. 120) • 2♀♀; Tbilisi; N41.77091°, E44.76877°; 437 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 5 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012472, 1012473. Shida Kartli • 2♂♂, 3♀♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.98477°, E44.13892°; 696 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, garbage; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018720, 1018721, 1018722, 1018723, 1018724. Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden, rock pile; leg. S. Otto; 11 Aug.; KVS 260 • 1♀; N41.64348°, E45.00289°; 450 m a.s.l.; pseudosteppe garden; leg. T. Shetekauri; 1 Jun. 2008; KBS 189.

Genetics. Seven nearly identical barcodes from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012472, 1012473, 1018720, 1018721, 1018722, 1018723, and 1018724 (BOLD:AAG0863, mean *p*-distance 0.2%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. sticta* from Germany (BOLD:AAG0863, mean *p*-distance 0.26%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously known from Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *C. sticta* from Georgia.

***Cryptachaea riparia* (Blackwall, 1834)**

GEORGIA – Guria region • 1♀; Ozurgeti Mun., Gaghma Dvabzu Vill., N41.93438°, E42.05894°, 200 m a.s.l.; settlement; leg. G. Makharadze; 14.-22 Apr. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004186.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1004186 (BOLD:ACX0542), identical to the COI genes of *C. riparia* from Bulgaria with a Private status and of another specimen from an unknown place of origin in BOLD Systems (BOLD:ACX0542).

Remarks. Species with a Palaearctic distribution (except for North Africa, Central Asia, and the Middle East) (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it was known only from the Abkhazia region. It is the first record of *C. riparia* from the Guria region and the second in Georgia.

*****Dipoena torva* (Thorell, 1875)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.76990°, E44.77041°; 440 m a.s.l.; mixed forest, tree; leg. A. Seropian; 6 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010361 (Fig. 121).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010361 (BOLD:ACB2315) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *D. torva* from Finland (BOLD:ACB2315, *p*-distance 0.61%).

Remarks. European species with a record from Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *D. torva* from the Caucasus.

****Enoplognatha mediterranea* Levy & Amitai, 1981**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.9801°, E44.1907°; 611 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-chris-*

ti dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 14 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023943. Tbilisi • 3♂♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.77702°, E44.70652°; 654 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035456 (Figs 122–124), 1035457, 1035458. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Mtskheta Mun., Shiomghvime; N41.8619°, E44.6404°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035803. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP; Mijnskure; N41.1127°, E46.6461°; 101 m a.s.l.; semidesert; J.-P. Kaitila and J. Junnilainen; 22 May 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035803.

Genetics. A single barcode from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1023943 (BOLD:AAN2962) identical in BOLD Systems to the COI of *E. parathoracica* from Turkey with an Early-Release status, that clearly belongs to the same species as the material from Georgia. There are no barcodes of the correctly determined *E. mediterranea* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. This species is distributed from Greece east to Iran and south to Israel (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously reported from Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Enoplognatha quadripunctata* Simon, 1885**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂, 2♀♀; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareji Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 387, KBS 204.

Remarks. This species has a disjunct distribution from the west Mediterranean to the east Mediterranean, the Caucasus, Iran, and Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is recorded from the Abkhazia region (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *E. quadripunctata* from the Kakheti region and the second in Georgia.

****Enoplognatha serratosignata* (L. Koch, 1879)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; E of Gori, Uplistsikhe; N41.96815°, E44.20660°; 641 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. A. Zukakishvili; 26 May 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004200. Tbilisi • 1♂, 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.7660°, E44.7671°; 470 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 2 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023287 (Figs 125–126), 1023288 (Fig. 127).

Genetics. Two identical barcodes from the specimens CaBOL ID-s 1023287, 1023288 (BOLD:AFH1023) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *E. serratosignata* from Norway (BOLD:ACS0144; *p*-distance 1.23%).

Remarks. Species with a disjunctive Palaearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from a single locality in Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record from Georgia.

***Enoplognatha thoracica* (Hahn, 1833)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Kiketi; N41.6359°, E44.64028°; 1122 m a.s.l.; forest edge, under stone; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 4 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009803 • 3♂♂; Tbilisi;

Figures 122–124. *Enoplognatha mediterranea*, male (122: left palp, retrolateral view; 123: same, ventral view; 124: chelicerae, posterior view).

N41.7709°, E44.7668°; 449 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Dec. 2021; (adult 18 Jan. 2022); CaBOL-IDs 1020714, 1020715, 1020716 • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.778°, E44.701°; 270 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. A. Seropian, E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 17 Jul. 2019. • 1♀; Tbilisi, Dighomi Vill.; N41.778°, E44.701°; 270 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. A. Seropian, E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 17 Jul. 2019. Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP, Korolistavi Vill.; N41.642°, E41.743°; 200 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 18 Jul. 2019 • 1♀; Keda Mun., Kveda Chkhutuneti Vill.; N41.502°, E41.851°; 270 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 19 Jul. 2019 Genetics. We obtained two identical barcodes from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1020714 and 1020715 (BOLD:) that appeared to be identical to the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *E. thoracica* from Turkey with an Early-Release status.

Remarks. Palearctic species, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In the Caucasus, this species was previously recorded from N Caucasus

and Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *E. thoracica* from the Adjara and Tbilisi.

Episinus truncatus Latreille, 1809

GEORGIA – Guria • 4♂♂, 1♀, 4juv; Ozurgeti Mun., Gaghma Dvabzu Vill.; N41.93438°, E42.05894°; 200 m a.s.l.; 20 Apr. 2020; leg. G. Makharadze; CaBOL-IDs 1004183, 1004184, 1004185. Adjara • 4♂♂; Khelvachauri Mun., Sarpi Vill.; N41.52139°, E41.55194°; 100 m a.s.l.; steep slope near road; leg. S. Otto; 17 Aug. 2007; KVS 280. Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., (Chachuna Managed Reserve, Dalis Mta Reservoir; N41.2764°, E45.8884°; 273 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032546.

Genetics. Three barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004183, 1004184 and 1004185 (BOLD:AAN3143, mean *p*-distance 0.91%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems as follows: for CaBOL-ID 1004183 and 1004184 – *E. truncatus* from Turkey with an

Figures 125–127. *Enoplognatha serratosignata* (125: male, left palp, ventral view; 126: same, retrolateral view; 127: female, endogyne, dorsal view).

Early-Release status (mean p -distance 0.15%); for CaBOL-ID 1004185 (BOLD:) – *E. truncatus* from Germany (BOLD:AAN3143, p -distance 0%).

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean north to the Scandinavian Peninsula and east to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). An abundant species in the Caucasus with a lack of records from Armenia (Otto 2023). In Georgia, it was recorded from Tbilisi, Abkhazia, and Samachablo regions. It is the first record of *E. truncatus* from the Adjara, Kakheti, and Guria regions.

*****Euryopsis episinoides* (Walckenaer, 1847)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 4 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂; Tbilisi; N41.77166°, E44.76875°; 436 m a.s.l.; urban; tree; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 22 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012475, 1012488, 1012489, 1012490, 1012481 (Figs 128–129), 1012482.

Genetics. Six barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012475, 1012481, 1012482, 1012488, 1012489, and 1012490 (BOLD:ACC4682, mean p -dis-

tance 0.12%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *E. episinoides* from Portugal with a Private status (mean p -distance 0.05%).

Remarks. This species generally has a Mediterranean distribution, introduced to South Africa, India, and China (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *E. episinoides* from the Caucasus.

***Heterotheridion nigrovariegatum* (Simon, 1873)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1 ♂; Kaspı Mun., Kodistskaro Vill.; N42.0321°, E44.3785°; 810 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 26 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011204.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011204 (BOLD:AAM0012) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. nigrovariegatum* from Germany (BOLD:AAM0012, p -distance 1.38%).

Remarks. Species with a Palearctic distribution (Nentwig et al.). It is the first record from the Shida Kartli region (Otto 2023).

Figures 128–130. *Euryopsis episinoides*, male (128: left palp, retrolateral view; 129: same, prolateral view). *Lasaeola prona*, male (130: left palp, retrolateral view).

****Kochiura aulica* (C.L. Koch, 1838)**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP, Mijnskure; N41.11181°, E46.6462°; 95 m a.s.l.; steppe, sweeping; leg. A. Seropian; 17 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010003 • 1♂, 1♀; Usakhelo Look Point; N41.1263°, E46.6071°; 261 m a.s.l.; semidesert, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 16 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1023763 (Supplementary File), 1023800.

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-ID 1010003 and 1023763 (BOLD:AAL8204) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *K. aulica* from Turkey (BOLD:AAL8204, *p*-distance 0.46%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species with no records from Central Asia, most of the Middle East, and West Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Kochiura* Archer, 1950 from Georgia.

***Lasaeola dbari* Kovblyuk, Marusik & Omelko, 2012**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2363°, E45.2857°; 1298 m a.s.l.; broad-leaved forest, dead wood bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025535.

Remarks. *Lasaeola dbari* is distributed in Turkey, N Caucasus, and Georgia, where it was known from the original description from Abkhazia (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). It is the first record of the species from the Kakheti region and the second in Georgia.

****Lasaeola prona* (Menge, 1868)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Akhklakai Mun., Kartsakhi L.; N41.1926°, E43.2411°; 1822 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, sweeping; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 5 Jul. 2022;

CaBOL-ID 1026455 (Fig. 130). Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki ridge; N41.9834°, E44.1495°; 641 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 4 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035506.

Remarks. This species has been previously known in the Caucasus from Azerbaijan only (Marusik et al. 2004). It is the first record of *L. prona* from Georgia.

***Latrodectus tredecimguttatus* (Rossi, 1790)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7785°, E44.6946°; 764 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 20 Jul. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1010052 • 1♂; N41.7812°, E44.6978°; 785 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027277. Kvemo Kartli region • 1♀; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681, E44.8219; 479 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035868

Genetics. Two identical barcodes obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010052 and 1027277 (BOLD:AAU5366) identical in BOLD Systems to the COI genes of *L. tredecimguttatus* from Turkey and Bulgaria with an Early-Release and Private statuses.

Remarks. An abundant species in the Caucasus, lacking records from Armenia (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Kvemo Kartli region.

***Neottiura suaveolens* (Simon, 1880)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2juv; Dighomi park; N41.7699°, E44.7738°; 427 m a.s.l.; meadow, vegetation layer; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020284, 1020285 • 1juv; N41.7699°, E44.7738°; 427 m a.s.l.; meadow, vegetation layer; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 2 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1023289 • 1♂; N41.7695°, E44.7702°; 430 m a.s.l.; meadow, vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10

May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023877. Kakheti • 1♂(subad.); Dedoplistskaro; N41.4867°, E46.1350°; 716 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, vegetation layer; leg. A. Seropian; 19 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1023336.

Genetics. Three nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1023289, 1020284, and 1020285 (BOLD:AAO4800, maximum *p*-distance 0.51%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *N. suaveolens* from Bulgaria (BOLD:AAO4800, maximum *p*-distance 0.51%).

Remarks. *Neottiura suaveolens* is a species with a sub-mediterranean distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is reported from Georgia only (Otto 2023). The first record of *N. suaveolens* from Tbilisi and Kakheti region, and the second in Georgia.

*****Neottiura uncinata* (Lucas, 1846)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.76947°, E44.77374°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow, field layer; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 31 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011759 (see supplementary file).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011759 (BOLD:AEL1813), identical to an unidentified Theridiidae from France in BOLD Systems, presumably belonging to the same species. There are no barcodes of properly identified *N. uncinata* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one.

Remarks. Species with a Mediterranean distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record from the Caucasus.

****Pholcomma gibbum* (Westring, 1851)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.81034°, E44.69545°; 921 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020320 (supplementary file) • 3♀♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7809°, E44.7096°; 628 m a.s.l.; meadow, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1020786, 1020787, 1020790.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from North Africa north to Scandinavia and west to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus reported from Azerbaijan (Marusik and Guseinov 2003). It is the first record of *Pholcomma* Thorell, 1869 from Georgia.

***Phylloneta impressa* (L. Koch, 1881)**

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 4♀♀; Akhalkalaki Mun., Tabatskuri L.; N41.64434°, E43.59848°; 2000 m a.s.l.; montane pine plantation, branches; leg. S. Otto; 21 Aug. 2007; KBS 127 • 2♂♂; Ninotsminda Mun., Kartsakhi L.; N41.1926°, E43.2411°; 1822 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, sweeping; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 5 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1026456, 1026457. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 2♀♀; Mes-tia Mun., W of Bogreshi Vill.; N43.01121°, E42.82935°; 1600 m a.s.l.; montane; leg. S. Otto; 20 Aug. 2011; KBS 141. Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.7717°, E44.7688°; 436 m a.s.l.; urban; leg. A. Seropian; 28 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012534.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012534 (BOLD:AFH0637) nearly identical to *P. impressa* from France with a Private status (*p*-distance 0.31%).

Remarks. A very abundant Holarctic species with a record from India (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Platnickina tincta* (Walckenaer, 1802)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7695°, E44.7737°; 426 m a.s.l.; tree; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 12 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012512, – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1juv.; Aspindza Mun., Mirashkhani Vill.; N41.332886°, E43.246857°; 1272 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain; leg. A. Memishishi; 12 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035238.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012512 (BOLD:AAJ7456) identical in BOLD Systems to *P. tincta* from Turkey (BOLD:AAJ7456).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, introduced to North America (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). A very abundant species in the Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Samtskhe-Javakheti region.

***Robertus arundineti* (O. P.-Cambridge, 1891)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori; N41.9673°, E44.1195°; 593 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011192.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011192 (BOLD:ABY8367) identical in BOLD Systems to *R. arundineti* from Finland (BOLD:ABY8367).

Remarks. A very abundant species in the Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Shida-Kartli region.

***Robertus golovatchi* Eskov, 1987**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Kintrishi NP; N41.7391°, E42.1160°; 700 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under rock; leg. G. Bananashvili; 14 Sep. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1018150.

Genetics. There are no barcodes of this species available in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first one. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018150 (BOLD:AFH1370).

Remarks. *Robertus golovatchi* is a species endemic to the Caucasus with records from Georgia and Stavropol Krai of Russia (Otto 2023).

***Simitidion simile* (C.L. Koch, 1836)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7791°, E44.7152°; 591 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 24 Jul. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1011699. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1juv.; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.4370°, E43.3078°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, *Crataegus* sp.; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1032696. Kakheti • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., Sabue Vill.; N42.0566°, E45.1232°; 635 m a.s.l.; sweeping; leg. Cabol team; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031223.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1011699 (BOLD:AAN9117) identical in BOLD Systems to the COI gene of *S. simile* from Spain with a Private status.

Remarks. Palaearctic species, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). A common species in the Caucasus. Previous records in Georgia are from the Samtskhe-Javakheti, Kakheti, and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *S. simile* from Tbilisi.

Theridion varians Hahn, 1833

GEORGIA – Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Dusheti Mun., Matura Valley; N42.44441°, E45.07033°; 1500 m a.s.l.; grassland; leg. S. Otto; 21 Jul. 2007; KVS 64. Adjara • 1♂, 2♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, under rocks, vegetation; leg. S. Otto; 6 Jul. 2010; KBS 183, KBS 185 • 1♂; N41.67795°, E41.84806°; 260 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, Buxus sp.; leg. S. Otto; 8 Jul. 2010; KBS 186 • 1♀; Kintrishi NP; N41.7294°, E42.0775°; 1020 m a.s.l.; malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 23 Apr. – 5 May 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012784. Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti region • 1♂, 1♀; Tkibuli Mun., Nakerala Ridge; N42.38522°, E42.98487°; 1400 m a.s.l.; beech-fir forest, branches; leg. S. Otto; 10 Jul. 2010; KBS 188.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012784 (BOLD:AAG1791) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. varians* from Norway (BOLD:AAG1791, *p*-distance 1.37%).

Remarks. Transpalaearctic species, introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). In Georgia, this species is known to be distributed along the Black Sea coast (Abkhazia region) and the Greater Caucasus ridge (Kakheti region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this abundant species from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti, Adjara, and Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti regions.

Theridula gonygaster (Simon, 1873)

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂, 3juv; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, fern; leg. S. Otto; 7 Jul. 2010; KVS 337. Samegrelo and Zemo-Svaneti region • 1♀; 1juv.; Zugdidi Mun., Kolkheti NP; N42.33802°, E41.61131°; 5 m a.s.l.; canopy beating; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 Jul. 2022 • 1juv.; N42.33802°, E41.61131°; 5 m a.s.l.; canopy beating; leg. Cabol team; 31 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1033173 • 1♂; Poti (near Kaparcha R.); N42.0734°, E41.7146°; 3 m a.s.l.; leg. B. Chitadze; 27 Jul. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035844.

Remarks. This species is not native to Europe and the Caucasus (alien species) (WSC 2023). It was imported to Georgia (Abkhazia region) and has been established in the western part of the country (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. gonygaster* from the Adjara, Samegrelo and Zemo-Svaneti regions.

Yaginumena maculosa Yoshida & Ono, 2000

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.7698°, E44.7698°; 434 m a.s.l.; under bark; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 30 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020312.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1020312 (BOLD:AAO2325) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *Y. maculosa* from Turkey with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 0.77%).

Remarks. *Yaginumena maculosa* is one of the species with the Caucaso-Far East disjunctive distribution that has been recorded in the Caucasus from Azerbaijan and Georgia (Marusik et al. 2004). It is the first record from Tbilisi and the second in Georgia (Otto 2023).

Family Theridiosomatidae Simon, 1881

Theridiosoma gemmosum (L. Koch, 1877)

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♀; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67795°, E41.84806°; 260 m a.s.l.; Colchic forest, Buxus sp.; leg. S. Otto; 8 Jul. 2010; KVS 341.

Remarks. This species is distributed from the Iberian Peninsula north to Scandinavia, west to Japan, and south to Iran. Introduced to North America (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. gemmosum* from the Adjara.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833

Cozyptila guseinovorum Marusik & Kovblyuk, 2005

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.76924°, E44.77399°; 426 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 14 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010375 • 1♀; N41.76924°, E44.77399°; 426 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 3 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012479 • 2♀; Didgori Vill.; N41.7854°, E44.6765°; 799 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011190, 1011191 • 1♂; Telovani Vill.; N41.8005°, E44.6821°; 892 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, edge of deciduous forest; leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 12 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021029. Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Mtirala NP; N41.67632°, E41.87472°; 300 m a.s.l.; river bed, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 6 Jul. 2010; KVS 333. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Mtskheta Mun., Tabaruki Vill.; N41.7665°, E44.5978°; 1000 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, cliff; leg. A. Seropian; 22 Jul. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035845.

Genetics. Three identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011190, 1011191, and 1012479 (BOLD:AFH1839). There are no barcodes of this species in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. This species is known from the Caucasus (except for Armenia), Turkey, and Crimea (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is known from Abkhazia and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record from the Adjara and Mtskheta-Mtianeti regions and Tbilisi.

Diaea livens Simon, 1876

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; meadow,

vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025550.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1025550 (BOLD:AFH1151), nearly identical to the COI gene of *D. livens* from an unknown country of origin (BOLD:ACA5363, *p*-distance 0.15%) in BOLD Systems.

Remarks. This species is distributed from Spain east to Azerbaijan and south to Iran. Introduced to North America (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is reported from Azerbaijan and Georgia (Otto 2023).

Ebrechtella tricuspadata (Fabricius, 1775)

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Gardabani Mun., Gamarjveba Vill.; N41.64348°, E45.00259°; 450 m a.s.l.; garden; leg. S. Otto; 11 Aug. 2007; KVS 255. Imereti region • 1♀; Chiatura Mun., Mandaeti Vill.; N43.3284°, E42.1756°; 770 m a.s.l.; suburban area, malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 23 May – 5 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012811.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012811 (BOLD:AAP3238) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems erroneously determined as *D. dorsata* juvenile of *E. tricuspadata* from Germany (BOLD:AAP3238, *p*-distance 0.96%) in BOLD Systems. The second nearest neighbor is *E. tricuspadata* from Germany (BOLD:AAP3238, *p*-distance 1.08%).

Remarks. A very abundant Palearctic species, distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023).

Heriaeus oblongus Simon, 1918

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7812°, E44.6978°; 785 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, on vegetation; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027278. – Shida Kartli • 1juv; Kaspi Mun., Nichbisi Vill.; N41.8426°, E44.5310°; 700 m a.s.l.; meadow, sweeping; leg. Cabol team; 30 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032341.

Remarks. An abundant Palearctic species, distributed throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). In Georgia reported from Tbilisi, Kvemo Kartli, and Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *H. oblongus* from the Shida Kartli region.

**Monaeses israeliensis* Levy, 1973

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1juv; Vere R. valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 27 Apr. 2009; KVS 375 • 1♀; Dighomi cemetery; N41.771°, E44.767°; 446 m a.s.l.; leg. Karalashvili E., Krammer H.-J. & Seropian A.; 17 Jul. 2019; ZFMK-TIS 8008377. Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Chachuna Managed Reserve; N41.230663°, E46.140872°; 460 m a.s.l.; semidesert; leg. A. Seropian; 19 Jul. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035870 (see supplementary file).

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen ZFMK-TIS 8008377 (BOLD:AAN6269), with the

nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *M. israeliensis* from Turkey (*p*-distance 1.22%) with an Early-Release status.

Remarks. *Monaeses israeliensis* is recorded in Bulgaria, Greece, Turkey, Israel, Lebanon, Iran, Central Asia, India, and China (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is known only from Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *M. israeliensis* from Georgia.

Ozyptila atomaria (Panzer, 1801)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀ (juv.); Dighomi park; N41.76924°, E44.77399°; 426 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 3 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016885. Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9825°, E44.0872°; 588 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035469.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1016885 (BOLD:AFH1410) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *O. atomaria* from Finland with a Private status in BOLD Systems (*p*-distance 2.6%). The second nearest neighbor was *O. atomaria* from Norway (BOLD:AAY8248, *p*-distance 2.75%).

Remarks. *Ozyptilla atomaria* has a wide Palearctic distribution (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from N Caucasus and Georgia (Abkhazia and Samechablo regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from the Shida Kartli region and Tbilisi.

**Ozyptila claveata* (Walckenaer, 1837)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori, Kvernaki Ridge; N41.98477°, E44.13892°; 696 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland; leg. A. Seropian; 24 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018809 (Fig. 131). Kakheti • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2223°, E45.3034°; 806 m a.s.l.; leg. Cabol team; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031239.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1018809 (BOLD:AAY8249) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *O. claveata* from Slovenia (BOLD:AAY8249, *p*-distance 2.16%). The second-best match – *O. claveata* from Germany and Austria (BOLD:AAY8249, *p*-distance 2.45%).

Remarks. Distributed from the Mediterranean north to the Scandinavian Peninsula and east to Iran (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023). In the Caucasus, *O. claveata* was previously recorded in N Caucasus and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from Georgia. The female of *O. claveata* is unknown.

**Ozyptila scabricula* (Westring, 1851)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi park; N41.76995°, E44.77379°; 427 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 7 Nov. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1020305 • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7806°, E44.7000°; 765 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 3 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1009769 (Fig. 132).

Remarks. Palearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023). Despite not yielding any sequence information, morphological analysis revealed that both specimens belong to *O. scabricu-*

Figures 131–133. *Ozyptila claveata*, male (131: left palp, ventral view). *Ozyptila scabricula*, male (132: left palp, ventral view). *Ozyptila tricoloripes*, male (133: left palp, ventral view).

la. The specimens represent the first evidence of this species from Georgia since the previous report (Gegechkori et al. 2005) doesn't provide any collectional or reference data on species from the country.

****Ozyptila tricoloripes* Strand, 1913**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 3♂♂; Dighomi park; N41.76946°, E44.77374°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 15 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012563, 1020297, 1020298 • 1♂; N41.76946°, E44.77374°; 426 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 12 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012594 (Fig. 133).

Genetics. Four barcodes from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1012563, 1012594, 1020297, and 1020298 (BOLD:AAV5283, maximum *p*-distance 1.37%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *O. tricoloripes* from Turkey (BOLD:AAV5283, mean *p*-distance 0.5%).

Remarks. This species is recorded in Turkey, Russia (Caucasus), Azerbaijan, Israel, Iran, Kazakhstan, and Turkmenistan (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *O. tricoloripes* from Georgia.

***Pistius truncatus* (Pallas, 1772)**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂; Tbilisi; N44.7798°, E41.7195°; 440 m a.s.l.; urban, malaise trap; leg. GGBC (CaBOL) team; 15. – 22 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012833.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012833 (BOLD:AAO1827) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. truncatus* from Germany (BOLD:AAO1827, *p*-distance 1.22%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023).

***Psammitis ninnii* (Thorell, 1872)**

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♀; Kaspi Mun., Khovle Vill.; N41.8805°, E44.2557°; 1075 m a.s.l.; forest steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 29 Jun. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012634.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012634 (BOLD:ACU8868) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *P. ninnii* from Germany with an Early-Release status (*p*-distance 0.15%).

Remarks. Palaearctic species with a distribution range from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is an abundant species in the Caucasus with no records from Armenia.

***Tmarus piger* (Walckenaer, 1802)**

GEORGIA – Adjara • 1♂; Kobuleti Mun., Ispani II wetland; N41.86339°, E41.78367°; 6 m a.s.l.; Sphagnum bog, field layer; leg. S. Otto; 22 May 2009; KVS 407. Kakheti • 1♂♂ (adult and subadult); Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2223°, E45.3034°; 806 m a.s.l.; leg. Cabol team; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1031233, 1031234.

Remarks. Palaearctic species with a distribution range from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is a common species in the Caucasus, with records in Georgia from the Kvemo Kartli and Racha-Lechkhumi and Kvemo Svaneti regions and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. piger* from the Adjara and Kakheti regions.

***Xysticus acerbus* Thorell, 1872**

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Kvareli Mun., SW of Gremi Vill. (Kakheti region); N42.00272°, E45.65850°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic shrubland, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 1 Apr. 2009; KBS 194 • 2♂♂; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44942°, E45.37903°; 900 m a.s.l.; N slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 29 Mar. 2009; KVS 361 • 1♀; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 384. – Tbilisi • 1♂; Vere R. valley; N41.71609°, E44.72004°; 500 m a.s.l.; xerothermic slope, under rock; leg. S. Otto; 31 May 2009; KBS 217 • 1♂; Kojori; N41.6794°, E44.7078°; 1000 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. A. Seropian; 8 Apr. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1010349. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♂; Mtskheta Mun., Shiomghvime; N41.85519°, E44.66517°; 600 m a.s.l.;

xerothermic shrubland, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 3 Apr. 2009; KBS 197. Shida Kartli • 1♀; Gori, Kvernaki ridge; N41.9847; 44.1414; 668 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 4 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020823.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1010349 (BOLD:AAG1214), identical in BOLD systems to the COI gene of *X. acerbus* from Bulgaria with an Early-Release status. The second nearest neighbor was *X. acerbus* from Germany (BOLD:AAG1214, *p*-distance 0.15%)

Remarks. Palearctic species with a distribution range from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, this species is known from the Kakheti, Adjara, Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti, Abkhazia, and Samachablo regions and Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *X. acerbus* from the Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Shida Kartli regions.

Xysticus bacurianensis Mkheidze, 1971

GEORGIA – Imereti region • 1♀; Baghdati Mun., Zekari Pass; N41.8522°, E42.8080°; 2196 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 11 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032039.

Remarks. This species was described from Georgia and inhabits subalpine and alpine belts of Turkey, N Caucasus, Azerbaijan, and Georgia (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *X. bacurianensis* from the Imereti region.

Xysticus kempeleni Thorell, 1872

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♀; Kvareli Mun., Shilda Vill.; N45.7162°, E42.0043°; 513 m a.s.l.; settlement, malaise trap; leg. GGBC/Cabol team; 23 Apr. – 1 May 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012916.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1012916 (BOLD:ACC4741) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *X. kempeleni* from Italy with a Private status (*p*-distance 1.39%) in BOLD Systems.

Remarks. Palearctic species with a distribution range from the Iberian Peninsula to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from Georgia and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023).

Xysticus luctator L. Koch, 1870

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Kavakheti region • 1♀; Didi Abuli Mt.; N41.3600°, E43.7107°; 2223 m a.s.l.; Abuli forest, leaf litter; leg. L. Mumladze; 28 Sep. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012755. Kakheti • 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1025551.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1025551 (BOLD:AFH3142) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *X. luctator* from Germany (BOLD:ACU8210, *p*-distance 2.3%).

Remarks. Palearctic species (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded from Georgia, N Caucasus, and Azerbaijan (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *X. luctator* from the Samtskhe-Javakheti and Kakhet regions.

Xysticus marmoratus Thorell, 1875

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Gardabani Mun., Kumisi Vill.; N41.60794°, 44.8655°; 498 m a.s.l.; dry heathland, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 24 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016820. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; 2♂♂; Aspindza Mun., Pia Vill.; N41.4370°; E43.3078°; 1222 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018782, 1018783, 1018784. Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♀; Mestia, Ushba Mt.; N43.0944°, E42.6921°; 3123 m a.s.l.; soil layer; leg. L. Mumladze; 18 Aug. 2018; CaBOL-ID 1012752. Tbilisi • 1♂; Dighomi park; N41.7681°, E44.7717°; 413 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 12 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032346 • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7796, E44.6995; 772 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 27 Nov. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1020853.

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016820, 1018782, 1018783, and 1018784 (BOLD:AAF8321, mean *p*-distance 1.45%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *X. marmoratus* from Turkey many (BOLD:AAF8321, *p*-distance 0.92%).

Remarks. This species is distributed in Central Europe, the Balkans, Greece, Caucasus, Turkey, Ukraine, Russia (Europe), and Kazakhstan (Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from Azerbaijan and Georgia (Samtskhe-Javakheti region and Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *X. marmoratus* from the Kvemo Kartli and Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti regions.

Xysticus pseudolanio Wunderlich, 1995

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♂; Ninotsminda Mun., Kartsakhi L.; N41.1926°, E43.2411°; 1822 m a.s.l.; subalpine meadow, sweeping; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 5 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026454.

Remarks. *Xysticus pseudolanio* is recorded in Turkey, Bulgaria, and Georgia (Nentwig et al. 2023). This is only the second record of this species from Georgia and the Caucasus after Otto and Japoshvili (2018).

Xysticus spasskyi Utochkin, 1968

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti • 1♂; Martvili Mun., Lebarde; N42.7382°, E42.5006°; 1625 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 30 Jul. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027118.

Remarks. This species is recorded in the Caucasus (except for Armenia) and Ukraine (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *X. spasskyi* from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region (Otto 2023).

Xysticus ulmi (Hahn, 1831)

GEORGIA – Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region • 1♀; Kolkheti NP; N of Pichori R.; N42.14758°, E41.82526°; 1 m a.s.l.; leg. S. Otto; 17 May 2009; KVS 400.

Remarks. Species with a Palearctic distribution (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is known from Tbilisi (Otto 2023). It is the second record of *X. ulmi* in the

country and the first one from the Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti region and W Georgia.

Family Titanoecidae Lehtinen, 1967

**Nurscia albomaculata* (Lucas, 1846)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi meadows; N41.7965°, E44.7871°; 518 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. L.-G. Japaridze; 1 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026424 (Supplementary File) • 1♂; Dighomi Vill.; N41.7812°, E44.6978°; 785 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 18 Jun. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1027286 (supplementary file) • 2♀♀; N41.778°, E. 44.701°; 740 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian, E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 17 Jul. 2019. Kvemo Kartli • 1♀; Gardabani Mun., Kumisi L. (S of Tbilisi); N41.577°, E. 44.824°; 476 m a.s.l.; dry steppe, under rocks; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 16 Jul. 2019. Kakheti • 1♂; Dedoplistskaro Mun., Vashlovani NP; N41.214°, E. 46.537°; 388m a.s.l.; semi-desert, under rocks; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 10 Jul. 2019.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1027286 (BOLD:AAV2942), identical in BOLD Systems to the COI gene of *N. albomaculata* from France and Turkey (BOLD:AAV2942).

Remarks. Palaearctic species, distributed from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it was recorded in Azerbaijan and N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *N. albomaculata* from Georgia.

**Titanoeca caucasica* Dunin, 1985

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Akhmeta Mun., NW of Akhmeta, Aniskhevi R.; N42.0830°, E45.3004°; 1022 m a.s.l.; meadow; leg. Cabol team; 30 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1031226 (supplementary file) • 1♂, 1♀; Akhmeta Mun., between Tianeti and Akhmeta; N42.064°, E45.064°; 1000 m a.s.l.; leg. E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 8 Jul. 2019. Tbilisi • 1♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.778°, E. 44.701°; 740 m a.s.l.; *Paliurus spina-christi* dry shrubland, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian, E. Karalashvili and H.-J. Krammer; 17 Jul. 2019.

Remarks. This species was described from Azerbaijan (Dunin 1985) and is also recorded in Turkey (Nentwig et al. 2023). It is the first record of *T. caucasica* from Georgia.

Titanoeca schineri C.L. Koch, 1872

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♂ (subadult); Didgori Vill.; N41.8011°, E44.6807°; 888 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, rock formation, under rocks; leg. A. Seropian; 4 Mar. 2021 (adult 4 May 2021); CaBOL-ID 1009781.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1009781 (BOLD:AAP3045) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *T. schineri* from Austria with a Private status (*p*-distance 0.2%).

Remarks. This species has a distribution range from Spain east to Central Asia and south to Iran (WSC 2023).

An abundant species, recorded throughout the Caucasus (except for Armenia) (Nentwig et al. 2023; Otto 2023).

***Titanoeca ukrainica* Guryanova, 1992

GEORGIA – Kakheti • 1♂; Sagarejo Mun., David Gareja Monastery vicinity; N41.44088°, E45.37847°; 700 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. S. Otto; 9 May 2009; KVS 383. Tbilisi • 1♂; Didgori Vill.; N41.7946°, E44.6844°; 858 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 11 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020896 (Supplementary File).

Remarks. This species was described from Ukraine (Guryanova, 1992), followed by a record from Rostov Oblast of Russia (Ponomarev 2008). It is the first record from the Caucasus. The present findings are the southernmost ones.

Family Trachelidae Simon, 1897

**Cetonana laticeps* (Canestrini, 1868)

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀ (subad); Didgori Vill.; N41.8117°, E44.6921°; 974 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest; leg. A. Seropian and G. Makharadze; 17 Nov. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1010040 • 1♀; Telovani Vill.; N41.80950°, E44.69064°; 850 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, under bark; leg. A. Seropian; 16 Nov. 2020; CaBOL-ID 1004182 (Fig. 134).

Genetics. Two identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1010040 and 1004182 (BOLD:AFH0540) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *C. laticeps* from Germany with a Private status (*p*-distance 2.14%). The second nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems is also *C. laticeps* from Germany (BOLD:ACA1478, *p*-distance 2.45%).

Remarks. *Cetonana laticeps* has a distribution range from Spain east to Turkey and Caucasus (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, this species is reported only from Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *C. laticeps* from Georgia and South Caucasus.

Orthobula charitonovi (Mikhailov, 1986)

GEORGIA – Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀♂; Aspindza Mun., above Vardzia; N41.37621°, E43.27626°; 1237 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rock; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10. Oct 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018785 • 1♀; Vardzia; N41.3529°, E43.2518°; 1315 m a.s.l.; steppe, Mtkvari R. bank, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 13. Oct 2021; CaBOL-ID 1032741. Tbilisi • 3♂♂, 2♀♀; Dighomi Vill.; N41.78086°, E44.70964°; 628 m a.s.l.; ravine, *Carpinus orientalis* leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 15 Dec. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1011182, 1011183, 1011184, 1011185, 1011186. Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 1♀; Mtskheta Mun.. Shiomghvime; N41.8619°, E44.6404°; 700m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1035799.

Genetics. Three identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1011183, 1011184, and 1018785 (BOLD:AAU2058) identical to the COI gene of the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *O. charitonovi* from Turkey and Bulgaria with a Private status.

Figures 134–140. *Cetonana laticeps*, female (134: epigyne, ventral view, *in situ*). *Hyptiotes gerhardti*, male (135: left palp, retrolateral view). *Zodarion morosum*, male (136: left palp, ventral view; 137: tibial apophysis, dorsal view). *Zodarion nigrifemur*, male (138: left palp, ventral view; 139: tip of the embolus; 140: tibial apophysis, dorsal view).

Remarks. *Orthobula charitonovi* is recorded from Turkey, the whole Caucasus, and Central Asia (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In Georgia, it is reported from the Kakheti and Samachablo regions (Otto 2023). It is the first record of this species from the Samtskhe-Javakheti and Mtskheta-Mtianeti regions, and Tbilisi.

***Trachelas minor* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872**

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.7699°, E44.7667°; 454 m a.s.l.; Paliurus spina-christi dry shrubland, xerothermic slope, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 20 Feb. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1021044.

Remarks. This species has a general Ponto-Mediterranean distribution, with records from Central Asia and West Africa (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). A common species in the Caucasus, known from Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Abkhazia and Kakheti regions) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *T. minor* from Tbilisi.

Family Uloboridae Thorell, 1869

Hyptiotes flavidus (Blackwall, 1862)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Gori; N41.9717°, E44.0962°; 747 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 27 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1016911. Imereti region • 1♂; Tkibuli Mun., Mukhura Vill.; N42.33407°, E43.08740°; 695 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest; leg. E. Arsenashvili; 2 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1018151.

Genetics. Two nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1016911 and 1018151 (BOLD:AAW9450, *p*-distance 0.15%) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. flavidus* from Israel with an Early-Release status (mean *p*-distance 1.78%).

Remarks. Distributed in the Mediterranean, European part of Russia and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2023; WSC 2023). The palp structure of the male from Mukhura corresponded to the drawings of *H. flavidus* given by Wunderlich (2017). In the Caucasus, this species is recorded only in Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *H. flavidus* from the Shida Kartli and Imereti regions.

**Hyptiotes gerhardti* Wiehle, 1929

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂; Kaspi Mun., Nichbisi Vill.; N41.8426°, E44.5310°; 700 m a.s.l.; meadow, sweeping; leg. Cabol team; 30 Apr. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1032343 • 1♂; Kodistskaro Vill.; N42.0312°, E44.3559°; 822 m a.s.l.; steppe; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 5 Oct. 2022; CaBOL-ID 1035490 (Fig. 135).

Remarks. Known from Greece and S Russia (Nentwig et al. 2023). The palp structure of the examined specimens corresponded to the drawings of *H. gerhardti* by Wunderlich (2017), who resurrected this species after examination of the specimens originating from Sochi, erroneously determined as *H. flavidus*. Presumably, previous records of *H. flavidus* from the Georgian Black Sea coast belong to *H. gerhardti*. This has to be confirmed after an old material is examined, until then, it is the first record from Georgia.

Hyptiotes paradoxus (C.L. Koch, 1834)

GEORGIA – Shida Kartli • 1♂, 2♀; Kaspi Mun., E of Kodistskaro; N42.03245°, E44.37978°, 900 m a.s.l.; steppe, bushes; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Aug. 2020; CaBOL-IDs 1004209, 1004210, 1004211. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 1♀; Bojromi Mun., Didi Mitarbi Vill.; N41.7465°, E43.58057°; 1700 m a.s.l.; forest; leg. S. Otto; 22 Aug. 2007; KVS 264.

Genetics. Three nearly identical barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL-IDs 1004209, 1004210, and 1004211 (BOLD:ABW9536, maximum *p*-distance 0.15%)

with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *H. paradoxus* from Slovenia (BOLD:ABW9536, mean *p*-distance 0.21%).

Remarks. This species has a distribution range from North Africa north to Scandinavia and east to Azerbaijan (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded in Azerbaijan, N Caucasus, and Georgia (Samachablo region and Tbilisi) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *H. paradoxus* from the Shida Kartli and Samtskhe-Javakheti regions.

Uloborus plumipes Lucas, 1846

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 1♀; Tbilisi; N41.7331°, E44.7926°, 433 m a.s.l.; steppe, abandoned building; leg. A. Seropian; 23 Aug. 2021; CaBOL-ID 1012629.

Remarks. This species is recorded from Europe, Caucasus, Africa, Yemen, Iran, and Pakistan. Introduced to Argentina, Philippines, and Japan (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is known from Azerbaijan and Georgia (Kakheti region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *U. plumipes* from Tbilisi and the second in Georgia.

Family Zodariidae Thorell, 1881

**Zodarion morosum* Denis, 1935

GEORGIA – Kvemo Kartli • 1♂; Marneuli Mun., Shulaveri; N41.3681°, E44.8219°; 479 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili, A. Seropian and A. Zukakishvili; 3 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-ID 1020868 (Figs 136–137). Mtskheta-Mtianeti • 2♂♂; Mtskheta Mun. Shiomghvime; N41.8619°, E44.6404°; 700m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 21 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035801, 1035802.

Remarks. It is a species with a Ponto-East Mediterranean distribution (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it was previously known only from N Caucasus (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Z. morosum* from Georgia and South Caucasus.

***Zodarion nigrifemur* Caporiacco, 1948

GEORGIA – Tbilisi • 2♂♂; Tbilisi; N41.7717°, E44.7688°; 436 m a.s.l.; under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 4 Sep. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1012550, 1012551 • 1♀, 1♂; Didgori Vill.; N41.7946°, E44.6844°; 858 m a.s.l.; steppe, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili and A. Seropian; 11 Jun. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1020893, 1020894. Samtskhe-Javakheti • 2♂♂; Aspindza Mun., Vardzia; N41.3762°, E43.2763°; 1237 m a.s.l.; meadow, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 10 Oct. 2021; CaBOL-IDs 1018786 (Figs 138–140), 1018787. Shida Kartli • 1♂(subadult), 1♀; Gori; N41.9776°, E44.0983°; 588 m a.s.l.; Mtkvari R. floodplain, under rocks; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 19 Apr. 2023; CaBOL-IDs 1035446, 1035447.

Genetics. Four barcodes were obtained from the specimens CaBOL IDs 1012550, 1012551, 1018786, and 1018787 (BOLD:AFH2061, max *p*-distance 1.13%) with

Figure 141. *Palpimanus* sp., female, live specimen from Mijnskure (Vashlovani NP).

the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *Z. thoni* Nosek, 1905 from Turkey (mean p -distance 5.9%) with an Early-Release status. There are no barcodes of *Z. nigrifemur* in BOLD Systems at the moment as we submit the first ones.

Remarks. *Zodarion nigrifemur* belongs to the *thoni*-species group (for group diagnosis see Bosmans 2009) currently containing six species (Bosmans 2009; Komnenov et al. 2016; Dimitrov 2020). It is the first record of *Z. nigrifemur* from the Caucasus. The examined material matched well the diagnostic characteristics given in Lecigne and Henrard (2022).

Zodarion rubidum Simon, 1914

GEORGIA—Shida Kartli • 1 ♀; Gori; N41.9782°, E44.1069°; 591 m a.s.l.; house backyard; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 31 May 2022; CaBOL-ID 1026326. Kakheti • 2 ♂♂; Akhmeta Mun., Batsara Nature Reserve; N42.2240°, E45.3004°; 817 m a.s.l.; deciduous forest, leaf litter; leg. N. Bulbulashvili; 28 May 2022; CaBOL-IDs 1035472, 1035473.

Genetics. A single barcode was obtained from the specimen CaBOL-ID 1026326 (BOLD:ACU7789) with the nearest neighbor in BOLD Systems *Z. rubidum* from unknown place of origin (BOLD:ACU7789, p -distance 0.35%).

Remarks. This species has a distribution range from Spain to the Caucasus and was introduced to North America (WSC 2023; Nentwig et al. 2023). In the Caucasus, it is recorded from N Caucasus and Georgia (Samachablo region) (Otto 2023). It is the first record of *Z. rubidum* from the Shida Kartli and Kakheti regions and only the second in the country.

Discussion

The utilization of a mitochondrial barcode region (COI) in animals has become a well-established standard for DNA barcoding and has been employed for re-identifying specimens and screening for potential new species candidates.

Until now, only two extensively inclusive barcoding datasets have been published for spiders, encompassing Canada (Blagoev et al. 2015) and Germany (Astrin et al. 2016). Additionally, spider barcode datasets are available to a lesser extent for Pakistan (Ashfaq et al. 2019) and certain regions of Spain (Crespo et al. 2018). Earlier research indicates that the accuracy of spider identification through DNA barcodes is approximately 95% (Candek and Kuntner 2015) and proposes a widely accepted threshold for genetic distance between arthropod species to be 3% (Herbert et al. 2003). In order to ensure dependable identifications, we have therefore adopted an integrative taxonomic approach, where the identifications are thoroughly reviewed and monitored both morphologically and molecularly.

From the resulting 283 COI barcodes from 150 species, several are worth noting due to the identification problems solely through COI subunit: interspecific lumps (*Clubiona alpicola* Kulczyński, 1882/*C. frutetorum* (mean p -distance 4.54%), (*Clubiona caucasica*/*C. caerulescens* (mean p -dist. 1.62%), *Walckenaeria alticeps* (Denis, 1952)/*W. antica* (Wider, 1834) (mean p -dist. 1.6%), *Pardosa saltans* Töpfer-Hofmann, 2000/*P. lugubris* (Walckenaer, 1802) (p -dist. 3.21%)/*P. alacris* (C.L. Koch, 1833) (p -dist. 3.5%), *Leptorchestes berlinensis* (C.L. Koch, 1846)/*L. sikorskii* Prószyński, 2000 (p -dist. 1.7%), *Enoplognatha mediterranea* Levy & Amitai, 1981/*E. parathoracica* Levy & Amitai, 1981 (p -distance 0%)); intraspecific genetic distances larger than 3.0% (*Callilepis nocturna* (Linnaeus, 1758) (p -dist. 3.37%), *Civizelotes caucasius* (L. Koch, 1866) (mean p -dist. 3.17%), *Gnaphosa steppica* Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992 (p -dist. 3.86%), *Haplodrassus silvestris* (Blackwall, 1833) (p -dist. 4.43%), *Zelotes longipes* (L. Koch, 1866) (p -dist. 3.08%), *Leptorchestes berlinensis* (C.L. Koch, 1846) (p -dist. 3.23%), *Phlegra cinereofasciata* (Simon, 1868) (3.26%))

As a result of the present survey, one family (Palpimanidae), 25 genera (namely *Palpimanus*, *Porrhoclubiona*, *Stegodyphus*, *Anagraphis*, *Callilepis*, *Iberina*, *Baryphyma*, *Erigonoplus*, *Plesiophantes*, *Poecilonea*, *Tallusia*, *Tiso*, *Mesiotelus*, *Wadicosa*,

Silhouettella, *Orchestina*, *Bianor*, *Cyrba*, *Icius*, *Mogrus*, *Plexippoides*, *Saitis*, *Coscinida*, *Kochiura*, *Pholcomma*) and 100 species of spiders were recorded in Georgia for the first time, including 5 new genera (*Iberina*, *Orchestina*, *Icius*, *Saitis*, *Coscinida*), and 18 species (*Iberina montana*, *Baryphyma proclive*, *Orchestina pavesiiformis*, *Icius hamatus*, *Saitis tauricus*, *Coscinida tibialis*, *Clubiona frutetorum*, *Haplodrassus orientalis*, *Micaria subopaca*, *Theonina cornix*, *Walckenaeria corcniculans*, *Agroeca brunnea*, *Pardosa saltans*, *Pseudeuophrys vafra*, *Dipoena torva*, *Neottiura uncinata*, *Titanoeca ukrainica*, *Zodarion nigrifemur*) records for the Caucasus region. In addition, records of 7 species (*Palpimanus* sp., *Mesiotelus caucasicus*, *Silhouettella osmaniye*, *Walckenaeria bifasciculata*, *Titanoeca caucasica*, *Orchestina pavesiiformis*, *Zodarion nigrifemur*) represent the northernmost limits of their ranges, while records of 6 species (*Enoplognatha mediterranea*, *Gnaphosa caucasica*, *Panamomops sulcifrons*, *Troglohyphantes birsteini*, *Attulus ammophilus*, *Titanoeca ukrainica*) represent the southernmost limits of their distribution; one species (*Sibianor turkestanicus*) represent the westernmost limits of their known range; five species (*Iberina montana*, *Baryphyma proclive*, *Icius hamatus*, *Saitis tauricus*) represent the easternmost limits of their ranges; four species (*Micaria subopaca*, *Theonina cornix*, *Walckenaeria corcniculans*, *Pseudeuophrys vafra*) represent the southeasternmost distributional limits; and one species (*Neottiura uncinata*) represent the northeasternmost limits of their ranges. At least three species (*Baryphyma proclive*, *Pritha pallida*, and *Zelotes khostensis*) are indicated to have an Italo-Caucasian disjunctive distribution.

Whereas 25 Linyphiidae species recorded for the first time in Georgia are not a surprise due to their small sizes, dispersal abilities, and secretive way of life, among the rest of the species-rich families leading an active and open lifestyle, Salticidae surprisingly stand out with 23 new country records.

Most of the new records originated from semiarid or arid habitats. This is explained due to the very limited studies performed in the central, central-southern, and southeastern parts of Georgia, thus leaving many more species unexplored or undescribed.

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Supplementary material

Authors: Seropian A (2023)

Data type: .docx

Explanation note: The file contains photographs of the genitalia/habitus of some species that are new to Georgia and have not been represented by drawings in the main article.

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